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Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

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Report on implementation of TAISs in ARUs

Deliverable D6.2

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UNIMED, Mediterranean Universities Union

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About RAISD	
Call (part) identifier	H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2018
Topic	MIGRATION-08-2018 Addressing the challenge of forced displacement
Fixed EC Keywords	Globalisation, migration, interethnic relations
<p><i>Forced displacement crises overcome societies and institutions all over the world. Pushed by the urgencies rather than events, solutions are frequently reactive, partial, and disregard some groups. The project 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' (RAISD) aims at identifying highly Vulnerable Groups (VG) among these forcibly displaced people, analysing their specific needs, and finding suitable practices to address them. The concept of 'vulnerability context' considers the interplay between the features of these persons and their hosting communities, their interactions and experiences, and how different solutions for attention and inclusion affect them. As a result of this work, a methodology to carry out these studies will be developed. These goals are aligned with the call. They pursue characterizing these migrations and developing suitable aid strategies for them. The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) frames the project. It proposes that all actors (including civil society) co-design actions, transversely integrates the gender perspective, and supports sustainability. Our research strategy will be based on methodological triangulation (i.e. the combined application of several methodologies). We will implement it through a specific participatory action research approach to fulfil the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models. The team will work as a network of units in countries along migration routes. The units will promote the VG people' involvement, so they can speak with their own voices, gather information, and test practices. Work will rely on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. Automated learning and data mining will help to provide evidence-based recommendations, reducing a priori biases. A software tool will support collaboration, continuing previous H2020- funded RRI work.</i></p>	

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Executive Summary

The goal of this deliverable is to summarise the key issues related to the implementation of the TAIS by the seven ARUs constituting the operational structure put in place by the RAISD project. The document focusses both on the process of setting up the ARUs and of the implementation of the TAIS by each ARU, trying to identify the main problems encountered, the success factors and the lessons learnt, the impact of the COVID-19 breakout and the future of the ARUs after the project ends.

In order to achieve this goal, the document is structured as follows:

The first section explains the methodology adopted by the Task Leader to collect and elaborate the necessary information for the document, specifying the key issues addressed and the information sources. Each one of the subsequent sessions focusses on one of the seven ARUs, presenting the results of the data gathered, thus contributing to the assessment of the progresses made and of the main difficulties encountered. A relevant paragraph in each ARU section is dedicated to the impact of the COVID-19 outbreak and to the way the ARUs reacted in order to proceed with the work. Also, a relevant question is the sustainability of the action which is addressed in a specific paragraph. In the last section, some overall conclusions are drawn from the analysis of the seven ARUs' outputs.

1 Methodological approach for this deliverable

This document, titled “Report on implementation of TAISs in ARUs” is the main deliverable stemming out of task T6.3 “TAIS implementation”, which is defined as follows in the Description of Work of the RAISD project:

T6.3 will carry out the actual implementation of TAIS using the project resources. According to the action research approach of the work methodology, they will perform the specific adaptations, and react to the local context. This task includes for each ARU:

- *Selecting TAISs (or developing new ones) to address the needs identified in T6.1.*
- *Carrying out the relevant adaptations.*
- *Adding adaptations to the description of TAIS or VCs when relevant.*
- *Implementing TAISs.*
- *Evaluating the impact of TAISs, compared with traditional practices, on addressing the needs. Use the criteria provided by WP7.*

The description of these items constitutes D6.2.

According to this definition, the task leader UNIMED adopted the following methodology:

1. The list of issues to be addressed for each ARU was defined, based on the bullet points listed above.
2. The sources of information were defined.
3. The information was collected and analysed.
4. For each one of the seven ARUs, the corresponding section of the deliverable was compiled.
5. Finally, some overall conclusions were drawn.

In this section we provide details on how each one of the above-mentioned steps was implemented

- A. The list of issues to be addressed for each ARU was defined, based on the bullet points listed above.

After thorough consultations with the coordinator and the WP7 leader (for the evaluation aspects) and in order to fulfil the above-mentioned goals of the Deliverable, the following list of information items to be collected from each ARU was defined:

- Building of the ARUs: from guidelines to stakeholders’ selection and engagement.
- ARUs way of working: meetings, exchanges, and decision-making process.
- How were the TAIS defined by the ARU members.
- How the ARUs started working with their TAIS, and who implemented it.
- What was good and what went wrong in the TAIS.
- Core results of the TAIS implementation and potential impact on beneficiaries.
- Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the ARUs’ activities.
- Sustainability of the ARUs’ work after the project ends and how to keep them alive.

B. The sources of information were defined.

The next point was to decide where the relevant information should be found or collected. The following choices were made:

- The reference document for the setting up of the ARU was the "Guidebook for ARUs' establishment". Delivered in July 2019, by UNIMED as part of Task 6.1 "Establishing ARUs".
- A relevant effort in collecting information about the ARUs' work was done to elaborate D7.1 "Research stories from ARUs: report and analysis".
- In 2020, UNIMED collected information from ARU leaders concerning the process of setting up their ARUs: this produced for each unit a document known as "ANNEX IV ARUL reporting".
- And finally and more importantly, the Leader of WP5, Menedék, launched a thorough information collection campaign in the second part of 2021 through a questionnaire known as "Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies V1_TAIS Final Report, 2021" filled in by each ARU leader, also known as "The TAIS Tool". In view of the elaboration of D6.2 (this deliverable) UNIMED proposed some additional questions to be included in the TAIS tool, which facilitated the task of collecting the necessary information.

C. The information was collected and analysed.

Hence the information contained in this document derives from an analysis, selection and elaboration of the above-mentioned information.

D. For each one of the seven ARUs, the corresponding section of the deliverable was compiled.

E. Finally, some overall conclusions were drawn.

2 The Spanish ARU - Complutense University of Madrid

2.1 *Building of the ARU*

The Spanish ARU was set at the Complutense University of Madrid, using the facilities offered by the university itself. The UCM team counted on several experts in Social and Computer Sciences, with a background in RRI and forced migration to start the work of the ARU. UCM team was able to leverage on previous experience in research projects and innovation actions to activate contacts and participants. The first ARU meeting took place in July 2019. Later, with the COVID-19 outbreak, the meetings were all held online. Both in face to face and virtual ARU meetings, all attendees were divided into working groups to discuss about the different issues that were posed. The Spanish ARU has always worked as an open structure, welcoming experts and actors from different fields due to their interesting profiles, being them experts in dealing with the detected vulnerable group, with forced displaced people, or upon recommendation of other ARU members.

The process of engagement of stakeholders was an ongoing process along the years. As an example, some institutions, specialists, and civil society activists, for example already working with Sub-Saharan women, were identified later in the project, once that this vulnerable group was chosen for the TAIS. Examples of the ARU actors include UNHCR, Red Cross Spain, and Madrid City Council. The most difficult helixes to involve were companies/businesses, public administrations, and individual FDP. In the specific case of the Spanish ARU, it was crucially important to engage beneficiaries of the TAIS, to avoid re-victimisation and to comply with the principles of the project methodology. However, especially for the FDP, the change of residence prevented many of them from joining the ARU meetings with continuity.

As a result of the fieldwork and the discussion in the ARU, one of the vulnerable groups that was identified was Sub-Saharan women because of the special difficulties for inclusion during transit and destination countries: violence, racism, gender discrimination, language, and greater migratory mourning. To these vulnerabilities, being single mothers or family charges can be added. On the other hand, all interviewees during the fieldwork highlighted the difficulty of finding a decent and stable job in Spain. The aim of this TAIS is to develop skills to promote the socioeconomic inclusion of sub-Saharan refugee women or applicants for international protection in Spain. The women beneficiaries are the principal actors, the centre of the action. All resources are at their disposal. The TAIS focuses on empowering the group of beneficiaries and promoting their autonomy. It is a training and support process with two courses of action: 1. In terms of entrepreneurship, so that they can create a collective productive project (cooperative). 2. Strengthening of abilities and preparation for a greater employability and professional growth.

2.2 *ARUs' way of working: meetings, exchanges and decision-making process*

Eleven meetings were held, with a number of participants ranging from 10 to 15 and representing a wide spectrum of stakeholders' types, including NGOs, the Red Cross, local authorities and research institutions. The focus of the workshops was as follows:

- I ARU meeting (02/07/2019) Identification of Distinctively Vulnerable People among the forcibly displaced arrived in Spain.
- II ARU meeting (06/11/2019) Preliminary results of the diagnosis.

- III ARU meeting (03/12/2019) Mapping of good practices and elaboration of TAISs work concepts.
- IV ARU meeting (21/01/2020) Continuation of the discussion of criteria and work concepts for the TAISs.
- V ARU meeting (25/02/2020) Start of TAIS design.
- VI ARU meeting (online) (12/05/2020) Progress in the codesign of the TAIS.
- VII ARU meeting (online) (22/06/2020) Progress in the codesign of the TAIS.
- VIII ARU meeting (online) (04/11/2020) Validation of evaluation criteria.
- IX ARU meeting (online) (23/03/2021) Definition of Vulnerability Context.
- X ARU meeting (online) (25/05/2021) Policy Recommendations.
- XI ARU meeting (online) (02/12/2021) Advancing in the collection of Policy Recommendations and Procedures.

As it can be observed, the activities concentrated on the codesign of the TAIS with the active involvement of the stakeholders representing the Quintuple Helix in a fully RRI compliant approach. As regards the working methods, by email, possible dates for the ARU meetings were proposed through Doodle to the people in our database. The date with the greatest possibility of participation was selected, also especially considering the helices of business and policymakers, as they are the most difficult ones to contact and they have a lower representation in the ARU.

Regarding the search for FDP participants, it is necessary to find people with a sense of security and a command of Spanish that allows them to participate openly with representatives of NGOs and other organisations in front of whom they may feel embarrassed or even intimidated. In future projects, it would be necessary to improve the empowerment and initial training of other FDP profiles to enable their direct and joint participation with the rest of the helices. It was also more complicated by online meetings due to the pandemic, especially during the total lockdown. Some representatives of the entities in the ARU meeting were always the same, other times they rotated or even changed, providing a greater diversity of perspectives. In the last meetings they tend to be the same, this also facilitates their active participation due to the complexity of the project.

Once the TAIS had been selected, it was necessary to add expert organisations in entrepreneurship and labour inclusion of vulnerable groups, and organisations working with sub-Saharan women.

The first meetings alternated between the Faculty of Computer Science and the Faculty of Information Sciences (UCM). Due to the pandemic, since the VI ARU meeting held on 05/12/2020, all ARU meetings have been held online through Zoom. The first online meeting was delayed more than desired as the final design of the TAIS was delayed, but it was necessary due to the overload of NGOs to assist their vulnerable groups at the beginning of the total lockdown. Avoiding physical travel could make it easier for some people to attend ARU meetings. At a certain point, the number of attendees at the ARU meetings decreases, but it could rather be due to factors other than COVID, such as sufficient advance notice of the meeting call, the specificity of the TAIS or the overload of the ARU members when a lot of information is requested from RAISD. Before each meeting, the agenda was sent to all attendees, as well as the information necessary to participate in the meeting. With those entities that were attending for the first time, a prior contact was made to explain the project and the most relevant aspects.

First of all, both in online and face-to-face ARU meetings, the UCM team presents a summary of the latest progress of the project, the TAIS and other relevant issues for the ARU members (also in order to foster their engagement), such as CRIOS or the future observatory. Then, the topic to be discussed in that session and the purpose of the

debate is introduced. For the discussion and debate stage, the attendees are divided into focus groups (through rooms in the case of Zoom), trying to ensure that there is a variety of RRI helixes in the different groups. One person guides the focus group, and another takes notes for the subsequent analysis of the information. A representative is chosen in each group, preferably someone not belonging to the UCM team, and the conclusions of all the groups are shared. The information provided by the participants is always collected in writing, but to avoid the loss of information, all sessions are recorded, and some images are taken with the explicit permission of the attendees. In the case of photographs, they are used to justify the existence of the meetings and to share the news on social media.

UCM team has developed a valuable and quite numerous ARU, but it is true that RRI and action research also hinder/slow down decision-making in the ARU, as mentioned in the TAIS Tool section of challenges related to methodology. Much transparency and communication efforts are required so that ARU members do not feel disappointed when their option is not chosen, the key issue to avoid the problem is the anticipation before misunderstandings may arise.

2.3 How were the TAIS defined by the ARU members

After conducting interviews with experts and vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced, as well as organising 7 meetings with 36 different organisations representing the quintuple helix of RRI, the ARU members decided that one of the most vulnerable groups in Spain was the one formed by Sub-Saharan women, and that employability was among their main difficulties. Therefore, the Spanish ARU decided to co-design the following TAIS:

Refuge of power: Sub-Saharan women's entrepreneurship and coaching program.

The aim of the TAIS is to develop competences to promote the socioeconomic inclusion of sub-Saharan refugee women or applicants for international protection in Spain as well as fostering the beneficiaries' self-reliance, autonomy, and general level of work market competence. The diverse problems of the vulnerability of sub-Saharan women were identified by means of the ARU meetings and the interviews with representatives for NGOs as well as with forced migrants of different profiles. In addition to the common problems of any forced migrant (such as difficulties in accessing housing and the labour market, as well as in understanding bureaucratic procedures), these women often face situations of physical and sexual violence not only in the country of origin, but also during the transit.

All sub-Saharan migrants are exposed to a long transit that can last months or even years. They must cross many borders and adopt different strategies to continue with their migration process. Often, during this process, they have no choice but to turn to migrant mafias that exert great violence against them. In addition, these routes to Europe include areas that are especially dangerous for women, such as Libya and the Mediterranean Sea route. This danger increases if they are pregnant or simply depending on their menstrual cycle. They are not allowed to get on the boat if they are menstruating, so they try to avoid it through pregnancy or taking medications without medical supervision.

As the interviews with experts and forced migrants reported, these women experience greater difficulties in host countries due to their racialisation and lack of language skills. To this, we must add the growing Islamophobia in Europe. These women often have family responsibilities. In some cases, they must leave their children in the country of origin, generating greater anxiety for not knowing about the well-being of their loved ones. Both during transit

and in destination, they run a high risk of being forced into prostitution, often with the intervention of mafias and human traffickers. In addition to the profound migratory grief generated by this kind of extreme violence, they are also exposed to sexually transmitted diseases. Also, women that have suffered genital mutilation present greater health problems.

They mainly belong to patriarchal societies that do not support them in their autonomy and individual life projects, but rather reject them, especially in cases of sexual and gender diversity. Sometimes, the cause for seeking refuge originated by their own environment that pushes them to female genital mutilation or forced marriages.

Once in Spain or in other European countries, the women find themselves immersed in a labour system that is far different from the African reality. These women are used to getting ahead and doing informal entrepreneurship (small local business) in their countries of origin. However, this informal entrepreneurship is not possible in Spain, where, in addition, the bureaucratic obstacles to starting a business are complex and unknown to migrants. That is why, together with the migratory trauma, such a different work context tends to marginalise them into underqualified jobs such as caring for dependent people, cleaning, or, in the worst case, forced prostitution. The personal worth of these women, their training and their previous professional experience are not considered.

For all these reasons, the Spanish TAIS aimed to re-empower these women and to provide them with the necessary training so that they could prosper in the labour market, increase their options, and even be able to start a new business by themselves.

2.4 How the ARUs started working with their TAIS, and who implemented it

A meeting was held in June 2020 with 12 possible beneficiaries of the TAIS in order to validate the design of the TAIS, to better understand their profiles, and to gather new needs and expectations (3 simultaneous meetings via WhatsApp videoconference, as it was the only tool they knew). The contents proposed by the ARU members for the training were mentioned to them and all were validated. Potential beneficiaries also expressed their needs and expectations, their availability, and their resources.

After analysing their perceptions, before starting the first round, a one-and-a-half month-long Spanish conversation course was included in the program and taught during the summer.

The context of health risk produced by COVID-19 was especially accused by the group of beneficiaries. From the very beginning, the design of the training had to be adapted to the online modality and for this, a new detection of resources was necessary. After identifying the new needs, each of the beneficiaries was given access to a tablet with an internet connection as a loan throughout the training.

The support of external personnel was necessary to give guidance when starting with the online modality, both at the coordination level to provide technical support for the management of electronic devices, as well as the implementation of new digital skills in the TAIS training content: use of online tools and applications, as well as the design of a common workspace in the cloud to be able to carry out the learning objectives designed for each session.

Emotional skills and emotional care have been necessary to empower the beneficiaries, to remain in the training cycle, and to accompany each other in these moments of uncertainty entailed by the lockdown and the social

isolation caused by the pandemic. In addition, an information session on hygiene and health prevention was implemented.

An adaptation strategy that was considered part of the success of this TAIS was keeping the continuity among the three rounds, taking advantage of the non-teaching periods to intersperse additional training and establishing interrelationships among ARU members, so that the beneficiaries could perceive and experience the whole program as a continuous process. As soon as it was possible, new measures were implemented to facilitate face-to-face meetings, this improved the motivation of the beneficiaries. For this, the social worker had a key role. This dynamic figure, in addition to constituting a lever of connection with the project, compiled the life stories of the beneficiaries, that helped the ARU to understand the social, economic, and emotional contexts of the participating women and to see their potential limitations: cultural context, family responsibilities, insecurities, relationship with the entities, legal situation, as well as their expectations after each training round of the TAIS.

Likewise, material resources and direct assistance were provided to the users so they could continue with the face-to-face activities. Among them were: masks and hydrogel, public transport tickets, and face-to-face accompaniment by the social worker. Finally, weekly reviews of the learning objectives were made throughout the three rounds to adapt the pace of progress in the following weeks. In addition, several open sessions were planned; the objective of them was to cover specific aspects identified as not assimilated during the normal lapse of the sessions or requiring reinforcement.

During the second round of the TAIS, a social worker was hired in response to the detection of weekly needs, mainly to reinforce belonging to the group and connection to the project, as well as to improve coordination with the ARU member entities that have contributed to the sessions. A company with experience in entrepreneurship with online pedagogical methodology, PAZ.ai, as well as the non-profit organisation Nantik Lum have actively participated during the second and third round of the TAIS to meet the learning objectives.

As soon as the restrictions caused by COVID-19 have ended and the face-to-face activity has been able to recover, the social worker has been crucial to be able to implement the new modality. In addition, she has coordinated practical activities, such as face-to-face visits to suppliers, as well as formal consultations related to the start of economic activity within the administrations of the Community of Madrid. Other ARU members have collaborated transversally in the second and third round of the TAIS, providing the beneficiaries with assistance in events related to social entrepreneurship for migrants, such as the Ashoka Global Summit. Finally, the Spanish TAIS has had the support of experts in certain training courses: university lecturers, economists, businesswomen, entrepreneurs, and volunteers who have helped to reinforce knowledge gaps or new needs detected in the weekly evaluations.

Table 1: Profile of TAIS implementers. Spain

Profile of TAIS implementers					
Total number:	23	Female:	20	Male:	3
Number of research staff:	6	Female:	5	Male:	1
Number of administrative:	0	Female:	0	Male:	0
Number of training experts:	15	Female:	13	Male:	2
Number of technical staff:	2	Female:	2	Male:	0

2.5 What was good and what went wrong in the TAIS.

Successful Elements

Apart from gathering information from the organising team and doing participatory observations, the Spanish team carried out outcome evaluation through in-depth interviews with two key service providers (an NGO and a social worker) and two representative beneficiaries (of different levels of learning advancement), adding to the results of the focus group that evaluated the TAIS after round 2 and receiving valuable insights and recommendations for future initiatives.

Service providers' point of view

One of the external service providers (a social worker) considers that all the beneficiaries have improved their professional and interpersonal skills and capacities, some of them have found new jobs and opened an online business during the TAIS training and mentoring program. Most of them have experienced great advances in terms of opening up and becoming more confident when applying for a job or interacting with a local administration. One of them even volunteered to participate in the RAISD documentary. This augmented self-confidence has also shown in more fluid and active participation and relationship with their core assistance NGOs, such as Provienda. Having mostly female trainers and lecturers has been an important success factor, as it has made the beneficiaries more confident and helped them to speak up. Both interviewees agree that the gender perspective has been well approached in the training and that is a key element of the mentoring program fostered by the NGO. The second interviewee accompanied part of the beneficiaries in the final phase of mentoring and mentioned the positive evolution in terms of self-reliance, as two of the beneficiaries found employment on their own, though she also states that one of the mentees still struggles with issues of self-confidence. The second interviewee says she has noticed how the participants have advanced from the dynamics of the group to a more personalised phase of individual attention and adaptation. When it comes to positive outcomes or rather benefits to the service providers themselves, the first interviewee mentioned that she had learned a lot from the beneficiaries, aspects such as cultural differences, local normative framework on migration and refugees and their condition. Both appreciate the cross-professional collaboration with NGOs, associations and lawyers that has brought them important new knowledge and contributed to a better understanding of the beneficiaries. Also, they have learned to adjust contents to the requirements and

needs of the participants, sometimes even within the lesson itself. One of the service providers evaluates the program success rate at 8,5/10 points whereas the other gives the TAIS program 7 points.

Beneficiaries' point of view

Also, the final evaluation included interviews with the beneficiaries, whose opinion is key for pondering the success level of the Spanish TAIS. One of the beneficiaries, a young woman (who profited very much from the program and has an advanced level of preparation), finds that the training and mentoring program have been successful in terms of providing the participants with tools for designing a project, looking for a job, and especially reinforcing their self-confidence: "Before, I just had ideas, but now with the development of the (class) project, I realised I need a plan and really get into it". She also thinks the training has given her consciousness about her own capacities "I become aware I can, I am able to do things" and that she has learned new skills, her Spanish has improved. She now feels more confident about the administrative procedures, she knows where to go to be attended. She got a new job during the training and mentions that the lessons on work interviews helped her to succeed. To summarise her conclusions, she would give 5/10 points to the program, mainly because she feels that even if the program was good, her expectations were not met, but still, the training has had an important empowering effect on her. The second interviewee feels that the TAIS program has been very good (10/10 points), and she appreciates all the contents. In her opinion, the courses have been mind-opening, and learning about the country and the language has been very useful, the lessons have broken her routines in a positive way. She feels better connected, receives work offers and has done job interviews. During the process, she also obtained the minimum vital income. "Before, I was very worried...", she concludes.

Conclusions from the coordination team

When it comes to processing criteria, we think that our TAIS program was successful in terms of accessibility and empowerment, but could have done better in terms of acceptability and viability as the contents and results did not fully meet with the expectations of the beneficiaries as the participants did not found a cooperative at the end of the TAIS. Still, the outcome was successful in terms of improving the beneficiaries' capacities and their package of competences, helping them to become more aware of their own strengths and empowering them to be aware of their capability. To underline some success factors, we would mention the implementation of the individual mentoring at the end of the program, the adaptation to the needs of the participants all along the process as well as the personal implication of the service providers and TAIS coordination team, and the personal growth of the beneficiaries, this latter difficult to notice in oneself and of which they might become aware of later on. In terms of social integration in the labour market and work opportunities, it improved for most of the participants. ARU collaboration throughout the whole process has been tremendously valuable, especially in detecting VGs, designing the TAIS and working on the evaluation criteria and process. "Our ARU was definitely one of the success factors of the Spanish TAIS".

Unsuccessful elements

Service providers view

One of the service providers finds that the program was launched in too much hurry and the team would have needed to have a deeper look into the beneficiaries' needs and expectations once they had been called to participate in the

training. After getting to know the group, she would have focused only on employability, leaving entrepreneurship training to the last phase if considered useful by the beneficiaries. Also, she was frequently in contact with the core assisting organisations that provide for the beneficiaries and, though many were very collaborative, some of them had a negative effect on the empowerment of the beneficiaries, as the assistants in these organisations sometimes did the course tasks for the beneficiaries. That was an important element of unsuccess as it contributed to a negative predisposition to performing with autonomy, towards the self-efficacy of some participants. The other interviewee argues that (even) more training on employability skills would have been necessary.

Beneficiaries' point of view

Even if the positive elements of the training and mentoring program were many, interviewee 1 argues that at the recruiting phase, her impression was different than the organisation team and that her expectations were not fulfilled as she thought the program would actually set up a cooperative with the participants, not just give the training to pursue this objective. Still, she recognises more positive than negative elements in the training. Also, she claims that the motivational gaps towards learning among participants were huge and some of the participants expected everything to be done for them. An element of improvement would have been to work more intensively in the motivational aspects and make the goals very clear from the beginning. Interviewee 2 has an all-accepting attitude, a positive evaluation of the program, though she underlines the necessity of finding a job as a priority of the training (which was not the case for all the participants).

Conclusions from the coordination team

The process acceptability and viability could have been improved if we had made adjustments of final objectives and contents right before the beginning, once the participants had been selected. In terms of outcome criteria, the pandemic partially hindered our ability to assist the participants in their social inclusion process, it became a goal harder to reach due to the activities online, lack of face-to-face action, missing visits to organisations and other foreseen socialisation activities.

2.6 Core results of the TAIS implementation and potential impact on beneficiaries

Regarding their expectations, all the beneficiaries affirm that they want to get a stable job so that they can buy a home in Madrid and be able to live without sharing a flat, without having to pay rent or without depending on an NGO. Two of them say that they would like to be able to save money to start an association and return to their country, buy a house there and give work to young people from their place of origin. Improving their social support network has been also considered by means of the TAIS, generating a support network among women from different places of origin and with different mother tongues. Finally, some of them have developed some kind of friendship ties with each other. Something relevant, since their spirits are low because they affirm that they are alone and feel lonely and that this affects them a lot when looking for a job or doing any other task. Moreover, it is very difficult for them to develop deeper levels of friendship in Spain so they cannot tell their problems as they would with friends, which makes them very sad.

Throughout the training and the mentoring program, an attempt has been made to improve their autonomy and responsibility for their self-learning, avoiding behaviours of dependence on the workers of the entities or third

parties. Its use in new technologies has improved, which also improves their communication and relationship with different entities and with the administration, increasing their social and personal autonomy. The improvement in their knowledge of bureaucratic aspects also allows them to interact with different organisations in a more proactive way.

The initial goal established in the ARU workshops was providing the participants with tools and skills for entrepreneurship, providing them a starting point for founding a cooperative, to directly improve their employment situation. Some of the participants had initially thought that the program would set up the cooperative for them and in this sense, they experienced some deception when they found out that the aim was rather providing the tools and capacitating them for entrepreneurship. Anyway, this initial idea was soon found to be a bit too ambitious as the beneficiaries did not find it feasible and within the reach of their possibilities, especially in terms of their economic capacity and confidence to start this kind of large initiative in a foreign country.

Another important goal was to improve the beneficiaries' employability with capacity building in terms of linguistic, professional, job-seeking, IT, administrative, business skills, etc., as well as fostering traits related to interpersonal relationships, self-confidence and gender awareness. The second goal was reached as all the participants improved their performance in most of the above-mentioned fields. Linguistic and communicative improvements are of great importance for these women, since one of the hardest situations that they remember from their stay in Spain is arriving in a country alone with a language that is totally unknown.

We can conclude that the program had a positive impact on the capacities building, self-knowledge and confidence of the participants, as well as on their awareness of tools and techniques for setting up a business and job seeking. In most cases, the training and the mentoring improved the beneficiaries' motivation for employment. In half of the cases, the participants found a new job or set up a small online business during the training period, so these can be considered fulfilled expectations. As an unexpected positive impact, we could consider that some of the participants launched themselves to found small online businesses. This has an important impact on their lives, since the expectations these women had were related to work. In terms of self-confidence, the empowerment test carried out in March 2021 showed that the participants felt they had experienced improvements and also, they felt they received more support from the group.

Nevertheless, the expectations to highly improve the beneficiaries' social engagement via personal contacts between them and with the persons providing training, entities they would have visited if it had not been for the COVID-19 restrictions, etc., could not be fully met. In terms of unexpected negative impacts, there was none of the consideration. Still, the lack of personal contact with the beneficiaries might have caused some frustration both in the trainers and trainees. All the women think that the professionals who work with them in RAISD and in the workshops, even by telematic means, behave very well with them and that they are very happy with the project, because this gives them the opportunity to interact with other women with their own situation and learn from the professionals who participate and also give them emotional support. Some say this project gives them hope to get a good future job. Three of the women think that the workshop professionals are happy with them because they do a good job, they are punctual, and they always do the task. And that for them is very important, believing that the professionals are very happy with the work they are doing. Four of the women affirm that perhaps the teachers want

them to be more participatory, because due to time issues or lack of knowledge of computers, they rarely attend the sessions, they do not do their homework and there are even times that they do not participate in the sessions.

2.7 Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the ARUs' activities

The Spanish ARU is headquartered in Madrid (Spain). In Spain, total lockdown began in March 2020 and the state of alarm was extended to the end of June. Due to that, we experienced an absolute impossibility to work with the target groups and to hold face-to-face meetings. The start of the lockdown coincided with the design phase of the TAIS, making it necessary to delay the final design of the TAIS and its subsequent implementation.

At the beginning of the lockdown, UCM team considered the option of remote meetings and consultations. However, the emergency work of the entities of the ARU, as well as the lack of technological resources and computer skills of vulnerable groups (that has been confirmed by Spanish ARU entities), impeded us from adopting online measures for the co-creation of the Spanish TAIS since the very beginning of the initial idea and throughout all the research and innovation process according to the principles of RRI. The pandemic severely hit and is still affecting several vulnerable groups, but especially economic and forced migrants with fewer support networks. Finally, the TAIS was designed and validated with ARU members and final beneficiaries through online and remote meetings and calls.

The situation in those first months was working in the middle of the unknown, since, as in the rest of the countries, the real dimension of the problem and its length were absolutely unknown. In the beginning, the authorities stated that the lockdown would last a couple of weeks. Fortunately, the UCM team remained foresighted and decided to design the TAIS according to the constraints of the moment, considering that the situation would take longer than anticipated.

The ARU decided to carry out online training despite the negative consequences it could have for training, as online training has a lower success rate. To allow the women to participate in the training, a tablet with an internet connection was given to each of them. In a context of total isolation, especially in the case of these migrant women, the TAIS also favoured social and emotional contact among peers.

The health crisis has brought about an economic crisis that has forced many small businesses to close. Due to the difficulty of starting a new business in this context, the UCM team decided to adapt the TAIS and to add a mentoring program not only for entrepreneurship, but also to prosper in the labour market.

After the total lockdown, a series of urgent prevention measures were adopted at the regional level, many of them affecting the freedom of movement in different neighbourhoods of Madrid. After the first months of the TAIS implementation, it was observed that many TAIS beneficiaries had difficulties engaging in the training program. Therefore, when possible, some face-to-face sessions were held, complying with all the protocols and without putting TAIS beneficiaries at risk.

From the linguistic perspective of these women who are not fluent in Spanish, online training increased the lack of understanding. This was solved with in-person support from the UCM team, attending one by one the beneficiaries who presented more difficulties.

2.8 Sustainability of the ARUs' work after the project ends and how to keep them alive

Some initiatives of the ARU can be prolonged in time. However, the main future perspective of the ARU is the online observatory. The project includes sustainability plans for the TAIS-related research methodology, especially in terms of keeping on researching current Attention and Inclusion Strategies (TAIS) of FDP and vulnerabilities related to diverse contexts. This is the core objective of the RAISD Observatory on Forced Migration, an international collaborative organism created among project partners that has already started its activity in March 2021 and that will continue working after the project finishes, with local branches and activities in project countries and driven by the coordinating partner.

Other initiatives related to the project, such as teaching innovation activities, with ARU members, FDP and migrants, as well as undergraduate and master students at UCM, will surely have a continuation in the future. UCM team will study the possibility of applying for funding to start new responsible research and innovation projects related to vulnerable groups, and where interested ARU members are invited to participate.

For all the aspects of future sustainability (as well as RAISD methodology compliance), the ARUs must be maintained throughout all the project, even after the TAIS finish their action. For example, the collaboration can continue by collecting policy recommendations, developing other initiatives (as mentioned above) and collecting ideas for the Observatory financing and actions. ARU members of all the consortium have a key role in sustaining the Observatory, which will be largely based on the volunteer work of project partners.

On the 4th of November 2021 Consortium meeting, Advisory Board (AB) members and RAISD partners offered some ideas for the project future sustainability and the Observatory, including the following:

- Especially small NGOs (many of the ARU members) are particularly interested in the project and in the TAIS practices, get inspiration and tools from the project. Therefore, it would be good for them to receive future training and resources from the Observatory. Also, the Observatory could collect the dissemination activities of the AB and ARU members, where they mention RAISD and talk about forced migration.
- It is hard to keep the action going without incentives, but this doesn't need to be monetary. Students are easy to engage, teachers can use the resources and ideas from the project (available at the Observatory website) for their lessons and projects. Also, FDP can be engaged as volunteers.
- Some of the project activities (TAIS) could be turned into field activities in the Syrian refugee camps in Lebanon and other countries.
- Reaching policy makers and offering concrete solutions would make the project more sustainable (and keep ARUs engaged).
- Networking and exchanging information, knowledge, and practices, making research data accessible for new studies and organising events, such as Youth for Change, would make the Observatory feasible and interesting for the ARU members.

3 The Italian ARU - The ARU/Competence Cell in CESIE

3.1 Building of the ARU

Based on the previous activities of CESIE in Horizon 2020, it was decided to start work of the CESIE's Action research unit within organisational Competence Cell (CC from now on). As a civil society organisation, CESIE's CC promoted a closer cooperation and co-creation practices among the main actors of the quintuple helix model, and this at both local and EU level (through the implementation of different EU initiatives). In this view, the CC aimed at coordinating and systematising CESIE's activities in the field of vulnerable inclusion, by supporting diverse targets and beneficiaries. In the frame of the RAISD project, the CC supports Highly Vulnerable Groups / identities among forcibly displaced people, by exploiting knowledge and practices in a more systemic way.

The Competence Cell is a sustainability element of the Horizon 2020 FoTRRIS project, which is in line with the RAISD Action Research Unit. Indeed, the strength of the Competence Cell relies on a smooth involvement of stakeholders. The systematic stakeholder involvement process has started already in 2017 (with the [H2020 FoTRRIS project](#) "Fostering a Transition towards Responsible Research and Innovation Systems") and continued within RAISD. As the Competence Cell body was officially established in April 2018, a wide network of stakeholders and target groups were already involved in several local and international activities of CESIE and were naturally engaged in RAISD, letting the working group naturally progress on the implementation of the TAIS. This has been possible due to the building of trustworthy relationships and successful collaborations that CESIE was able to put in place over many years of cooperation with identified stakeholders. Moreover, a number of stakeholders have been involved in the Italian ARU thanks to their involvement in other CESIE's activities, reinforcing the inclusion mechanism of the network. As an example, external stakeholders involved in the RAISD fieldwork activities have been selected with the support of CESIE's [Migration Unit](#). Also, actors of institutional, academic and societal impact are contributing to the work of the CC, such as psychological and health support services, hosting community and migrants' associations, and representatives of civil society. The quintuple helix is represented, and the CC had the capacity to involve new working group members as the TAIS planning evolves and adaptation were needed.

In terms of the ARU internal members, the selection / assignment process of the staff involved followed institutional procedures: each CESIE Unit designates 1 delegate PM to oversee and join the planning, implementation and evaluation procedures of activities. Plus, monthly meetings were held to support the definition of training contents, syllabuses, calendar, workshops, identify BP and monitor the TAIS pilot implementation. 3 staff members (including both permanent and temporary staff) are involved in the short-term operations of the CC, supported by other internal staff (such as CESIE leaders and experts). Internal people working in the Cell were selected based on the experiences: people with knowledge of transdisciplinary research, community building methodologies, with local contacts, good communication skills, project development skills.

Considering deeply rooted systemic barriers and the present historical political instability in Italy that might preclude stakeholders' active involvement, RAISD represents a great opportunity for the Italian ARU / the Competence Cell and its impact network to continue the work on migration and specific Vulnerability Contexts. The Cell uses community and bottom-up initiatives, creating a transdisciplinary network of practitioners to support local infrastructures and contribute to community building, capacity building and awareness raising. Indeed, the

Competence Cell takes advantage of a multitude of local partners that contribute to project implementation at different levels and emerge competences of the staff members of six Units (Higher Education and Research Unit, Right and Justice, Adult, Migration, School and Youth). External participants are selected based on their professional profile and link to local/national thematic networks.

3.2 ARUs' way of working: meetings, exchanges, and decision-making process

The CC was operational well beyond the RAISD project, being an element of a previous Horizon project (see details above). All research activities related to the RAISD Action Research Unit have officially merged into our Competence Cell, established originally in April 2018, with a special focus on migration and specific Vulnerability Contexts. Seven RAISD Thematic Committees were established by July 2019, directly referring to the Italian Programme and Policy priorities' as stated in the National Integration Plan for Persons Entitled to International Protection. The national priorities were discussed in several sessions by a variety of stakeholders to ensure that analysis and assessments of existing practices was approached from wider and diverse perspectives. The involvement of diverse esteemed experts and practitioners in the action-research model has allowed the accomplishment of quality in the data gathering, also in regard to the various methodologies applied, including a variety of analysis levels on vulnerabilities and contexts, identification of potential Good Practices and it contributed to different perspectives such as how to proceed when designing TAIS.

The full TAIS implementation with its 3 piloting rounds saw the active involvement of n. 19 local different actors for a minimum of 34 ARU planning and organisational meetings, counting a cumulative 162 attendees. Moreover, further 16 meeting sessions (14 in Trabia and 2 in Palermo) were held during the piloting of group 2. The combined actions of the CC aimed to further improve and expand the dialogue among institutions, bodies, associations, and grassroots who have been working together for years to construct inclusive processes for highly vulnerable groups in the city of Palermo. Moreover, the fact that most CESIE's projects are funded by European Institutions rather than relying on rather uncertain national or regional funding allowed the establishment of local trustworthy cooperation with quintuple helix representatives, that most certainly would have had difficulties in their initiation and long-term sustainability.

As the complexity of the project is very considerable, the ARU satisfied the need for a renowned systemic body that envisions and invests in the growth of significant long-term cooperation relationships and social networks, building a safe community around the highly vulnerable target groups along the inclusion process. The involvement of diverse esteemed experts and practitioners in the action-research model has allowed the accomplishment of quality in the data gathering, also in regard to the various methodologies applied, including analysis levels on vulnerable profiles and contexts, identification of potential Good Practices and it contributed to different perspectives such as how to proceed when designing and implementing the TAIS, Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies. The combined actions further improved and expanded the dialogue among institutions, bodies, associations, and grassroots who have been working together for years to construct inclusive processes for highly vulnerable groups in the city of Palermo. During the pilot experience itself, important direct and indirect synergies were created at local level with other institutions and centres that support the well-being, education, and autonomy of trafficked women. Collaboration was acknowledged by: the centre's psychologist and doctor, the Provincial Centres for Adult Education (CPIA) and Carabinieri (national gendarmerie of Italy who primarily carries out domestic policing duties).

Part of the decision-making process and continuously contributing to the further development and update of the definition of “Vulnerability Contexts” has been CESIE’s [INTEGRA Network](#) (committed to sharing experiences, good practices and initiatives to promote paths of accompaniment to autonomy for young and vulnerable Forcibly Displaced). Initial assumptions and considerations regarding contexts that provoke and/or increase vulnerabilities had to be reconsidered in time, especially due to the first, second and third COVID-19 outbreaks in Italy. The Network represented reliable primary source data, gathering multi-stakeholder perspectives on vulnerability as an intersubjective relation and dependent on actors’ viewpoints. Active members of the Network include all quintuple helix stakeholders’ representatives and migrant associations and individuals (currently 34 members from migrant communities/associations, civil society, private social organisations, entrepreneurs, and public institutions/local authorities).

3.3 How were the TAIS defined by the ARU members

Starting from the project’s consideration that institutions and organisations providing services to immigrants are not always aware of all the vulnerability factors that shape the needs of their beneficiaries, educational inclusion solutions are frequently reactive, partial and disregard some groups. Moreover, there is still a tendency for national educational policymakers and planners to ignore human factors, training providers too often assume to know and understand FDP’ learning needs, thrusting learners into one-size-fits-all solutions while ignoring those individual factors and circumstances (pre-migration, in-transit, at-arrival) that strongly affect educational achievements. In Italy, this reflects in a high number of NEET (Not in Education, Employment or Training) among FDP, consistent training dropout rates and lower female participation. CC staff members, together with selected stakeholders, engaged in a deep research process, interviews and fieldwork and ultimately developed the TAIS in the form of tailored learning paths AUCL.

The evidence for a need in “Change Management in Education Delivery Approaches” that could focus on local/regional manifestations of global challenges and on ‘local’ opportunities for solving them, was suggested by the RAISD fieldwork findings under the action-research approach, through 13 interviews with FDP (11 of them male and 14 females) and 11 Local Quintuple Helix Stakeholder consultations, to comply with activities of the RRI architecture process. External Stakeholders have been selected based on the mapping of the local knowledge actors and were invited to join Thematic Committees to analyse main Italian Programme and Policy priorities’ routes, as stated in the National Integration Plan for Persons Entitled to International Protection by the Ministry of Interior, Department for Civil Liberties and Immigration.

The research question raised after the literature, policy documents review, and interviews is: What are the most effective educational inclusion strategies for increasing participation and continuity in education among highly vulnerable displaced people currently living in the region of Sicily? Meeting individual needs is at core of the AUCL Strategy that adopts the novelty Selective Approach. The FDP, from now on intended as “co-experts” of the RRI based inclusion process, have the opportunity to self-tailor their curricula and co-design their own personal inclusion strategy, by default, as they are having a direct influence over their own learning path’s contents and modalities according to a set of individual variables (interests and aspirations, level of studies and previously attended programmes, language knowledge, logistics, and time availability, etc.). Therefore, the TAIS design is flexible in the training content and delivery modes so as to meet as much as possible the needs of different ranges of educational

attainments (from the highly educated to those with only a basic level of education, or limited to informal and non-formal), Italian languages proficiency and time availability.

The choice for addressing vulnerable women was a result of the context analysis, stakeholders' input and HVG fieldwork. Most female interviewees have been morally or physically neglected in childhood, raised in unhealthy or dangerous places or by people who are unable to provide them with an education. Issues such as forced marriage, abusive relationships, sexual offence attempts, forced marriages, threatening of Female Gender Mutilation (FGM) and other forms of gender-based violence are represented in women's accounts.

As a schematic representation of the TAIS development:

- TAIS identification process. In January 2020 the work within the ARU for the TAIS identification was launched. The ARU and Advisory Board member were informed about the Research outcomes and findings developed under D4.1 Vulnerability Profiling and D5.1 Preliminary catalogue of Good (attention and inclusion) Practices, which drafted aspects, elements, and criteria to be taken into consideration while planning the different TAIS ideas.
- Brainstorming TAIS. February 2020: Set up of four working groups led by CESIE's cooperation Units' representatives - while taking into consideration and consulting input and feedback as expressed by the ARU [Thematic Committees established during Fieldwork](#) (WP3).
- Benchmarking TAIS. March 2020: Each ARU working group was requested to benchmark their TAIS proposal against the actor-oriented criteria identified under D5.1, undergoing a quality check as a tool to check if the proposal would satisfy HVG's needs.
- Exploring TAIS. March 2020: ARU Working groups were requested to detail their proposal by filling in the "D5.2 preliminary draft and questions" as provided by WPL Menedék.
- TAIS selection process. April 2020: Ultimately the TAIS Strategy, including concepts and elements of most of the submitted proposals by the different working groups, was selected and agreed to be tested. Given the limitation due to COVID-19, the ARU agreed on an option that could offer and include knowledge resources and involve experts of all different thematic areas of interventions, and in the long term to be exploited and sustained by the use of the tool of a wider variety of vulnerable target groups.

3.4 How the ARUs started working with their TAIS, and who implemented it.

Stakeholders and CC members were involved along all the process, with continuous meetings (in presence and online) during needs analysis, vulnerability profiling, best practice identification and actor-oriented criteria definition. Refinement and adjustments were undertaken during the design phase but, most importantly, during the piloting phase and as a consequence of the pandemic outbreak. Besides the collaborations with the partners, further dissemination and communication activities were implemented through different online channels, platforms, and conferences.

In terms of staff involved in the TAIS implementation, the piloting was coordinated by CESIE. Due to the restrictions caused by the COVID-19 spread, most of the activities were performed either online or at the CESIE facilities in Palermo. The internal team was composed by a local contact person, a responsible for the stakeholders' involvement; a head trainer for the supervision of the content, methodological planning and logistics; a Trainers' Hub (3

professional trainers + 2 guest speakers); 4 professional Mentors to ensure individual and ongoing support for each of the 5 assigned mentees (2 of Nigerian origin, 1 Kenyan and 1 Tunisian), being representatives or collaborators of protected women shelters themselves. Externally the TAIS implementation was supported by the involved women support centres and by the Quintuple Helix representatives supposed to host a Study Visit. Advisory Board members supported the definition of learning objectives to be achieved and contribute to the participants' recruitment process. Three CAS centres were involved at the beginning of the piloting (trainers visiting their residential facilities) and two initially accepted to host the AUCL activities at their centre. Regrettably, due to the difficulties for trainers getting permission to enter protected women shelters and the COVID-19 lockdowns, there was a withdrawal by two of the centres.

The AUCL concept and design were not altered at its core between the piloting rounds and groups. The execution though underwent consistent changes in location, lengths, intensity and actors involved. In terms of types of collaborators, the first piloting round included the professional mentors' profile to foster community engagement. The AUCL Mentors were assigned to the following tasks and responsibilities: ensure individual and ongoing mentoring support for each of the 5 mentees assigned; collaborate with the training experts in the implementation of the educational project; accompanies and supports (physically accompanies, where/when necessary) the participants during educational activities on the days, hours and locations defined; help in the choice and support in the selection of the modules); take care of the attendance monitoring of the course, reports in real time and contacting the students in case of unjustified absence; cooperate with the experts who carry out monitoring or budgeting actions, ensuring that the intervention is carried out with responsibility and motivation; maintain contact with the training manager to monitor the inclusion outcomes of the inclusion intervention; participate in sharing meetings with other mentors and trainers involved. The second pilot round was ultimately implemented with and at CAS "Cooperativa Nuova Generazione" in the nearby town of Trabia (20 km distance from Palermo). Here the role of the AUCL Mentors was taken over by the CAS's own multidisciplinary team: coordinator, educators, legal operator, psychologist, mediator.

Table 2: Profile of TAIS implementers. Italy

1. Profile of TAIS implementers					
Total number:	9	Female:	6	Male:	3
Number of research staff:	4	Female:	4	Male:	0
Number of administrative:	1	Female:	0	Male:	1
Number of training experts:	3	Female:	1	Male:	2
Number of technical staff:	1	Female:	1	Male:	0

3.5 What was good and what went wrong in the TAIS

Successful elements

Accessibility

The piloting of "ALL you can LEARN" involved 27 Forcibly Displaced Women living and/or exposed to highly vulnerable situations and conditions, victims of human trafficking currently living in Sicily. Piloting group 1: 18 women from Nigeria and Tunisia, yet the ethnic and cultural backgrounds were much diverse. Adults: declared average 33 (18 to 59). Languages spoken: Arabic, French, English, Italian, Yoruba, Hausa, Edo, Swahili, Kimeru, Kikuiu, Esan. Piloting group 2: 9 women from Somalia, Comoros Island, Sierra Leone. Young adults: declared average age 19,25 (18 to 24). Languages spoken: English, Bambara, Arabic, Comorian, Italian.

Ease of access to training facility

The location of the centres/services is a very important element to be considered in terms of inclusion. In the Italian TAIS the CESIE's Training facilities in Palermo allowed a recruitment strategy that relied on the cooperation of local FDP/HVG relief, support, and community centres. The training premises were located near the bus and train stations, places which have always been very popular amongst migrant communities - therefore, more known and easily accessible. Moreover, the hired professional mentors were requested to accompany and support (physically accompany, where/when necessary) the participants during educational activities on the days, hours and locations defined by the AUCL calendar. Moreover, CESIE owns an internal childcare service for its employees, where participants' children could stay during the mothers' hours participation. Regrettably the service had to be fully stopped with the children during COVID-19 since early restrictive measures. Therefore, the lack of childcare services might have hindered some women from participating.

Non-discrimination

The AUCL activities were based on active participation methods in order to allow each participant to express. Since the language skills were quite different among participants, trainers tried to make sure that every participant could understand and feel included. The TAIS was held in three languages (Italian, English, French) that were constantly mixed according to their needs. Moreover, the participants access the online tool and are approached 'just' as adult learners with no indication in names or titles, or to their specific target profile "Highly Vulnerable People amongst the Forcibly Displaced".

Inclusion

According to participants themselves, participating all together in the training sessions was a good chance to have a good time together, to get to know each other better and to go beyond eventual rivalries and hostilities among them. In terms of social interactions and dynamics within the group of learners, there were little subgroups according to the country of origin and languages spoken. Nevertheless, there were no obvious dislikes among the subgroups. This was a favourable condition that allowed the trainers to create a good and collaborative working atmosphere.

Enthusiasm

TAIS was received by the working staff of the hosting centre as a very good change for the participants. They showed enthusiasm because the participants were involved in the course, and they wanted to participate. As the working staff reported, the women didn't show such an enthusiasm for the learning programs proposed to them before the TAIS. They even asked CESIE to continue the collaboration and involve the women in other projects because they can see positive effects in their life motivation.

Empowerment

Participants who took part in AUCL were women hosted in a hosting centre as trafficking survivors or still trying to get out of trafficking networks. The common benefits that trainers could observe among all participants are:

- Overcome language barriers.
- Connect in a more peaceful and authentic way among themselves and develop a better sense of collaboration in the group.
- Express their feelings.
- Develop a better empathy for themselves and for others.

One of the main aspects highlighted by participants was the fact that TAIS allowed them to raise a sense of responsibility for their own future and a motivation to move forward in their own lives. They felt more secure of themselves at the end of the course and, as they reported, this is an attitude that will improve their daily life and their work.

Moreover, the knowledge of the Italian language, the resources related to institutional, social, economic, health, and educational aspects of the Italian country have increased. One tangible resource was the knowledge of the use of technological tools. Beneficiaries found them extremely useful for their professional and personal lives. The course had a great impact in increasing women's language skills and autonomy. In addition, specific topics such as work gave them a greater awareness of their rights and duties. It was stated that the course had increased their desire to find work in the regular market and to be independent in the society in which they live. Participants underlined how this cooperation mode made them feel like the authors of their own personal and professional growth project, learning new transversal skills but also growing in terms of language and knowledge of the territory in which they live.

Increased cross-professional contacts as a result of TAIS

The combined actions further improved and expanded the dialogue among institutions, bodies, associations, and grassroots who have been working together for years to construct inclusive processes for highly vulnerable groups in the city of Palermo. During the pilot experience itself, important direct and indirect synergies were created at local level with other institutions and centres that support the well-being, education, and autonomy of trafficked women. Collaboration was acknowledged by: the centre's psychologist and doctor, the Provincial Centres for Adult Education (CPIA) and Carabinieri (national gendarmerie of Italy who primarily carries out domestic policing duties).

The RAISD experience led to further discussions within the ARU on how the TAIS novelty selective-approach in education could be boosted and further developed with the vulnerable target groups. The full TAIS implementation

with its 3 piloting rounds saw the active involvement of n. 19 local different Actors for a minimum of 34 ARU planning and organisational meetings, counting a cumulative 162 attendees.

Unsuccessful elements and/or unexpected limitations

Reduction in the beneficiaries number

AUCL was initially designed to be experienced by 20 women attending the course at CESIE's premises from October 2020-March 2021. Due to COVID-19 restrictions, piloting group 1 could host only 18 participants as a maximum of 12 people were allowed in a training room (9 pax + 2 mentors + 1 trainer). The actual downsizing of participants in group 2 allowed 9 participants to benefit from the experience. All participants of group 1 that had to interrupt activities in December 2020 were personally contacted and invited to restart with the new group in May 2021, but no learners returned as their priority is looking for jobs to gain immediate benefits and to provide for their families in the country of origin. Moreover, due to their troubled history, during the pilot implementation, there have been actual cases where women have left and never returned to the centre, and although all women are supported by an experienced team of psychologists and doctors, many of them have manifested considerable psychic distress.

Digital unpreparedness

External factor influencing the administration and accessibility of TAIS was the impact of COVID-19 within society. The pandemic diminished, if not entirely prevented, face-to-face activities. Participants of group 1 actually did not have the necessary skills, IT devices, and internet connection means to assist distance learning sessions. With group 2, since the first sessions, all activities were supported by technological equipment brought into the cooperative by CESIE, such as laptops and tablets. This made the participants' technological skills grow vertically and progressively and increased their curiosity and active participation during all the sessions.

Length of the training

AUCL Training hours had to be reduced. Initial design included 90 hours/5 study visits; the actual implementation though saw only total 40hours/2 study visits. Fieldwork research suggested that the lengths of a course should not be under 6 months of activities. Actually, this proved not being feasible in this specific case.

Change in the participants' recruitment model

Differently from the first piloting round, where women were invited to participate by their women day care centres of reference, for the second piloting round it was then CESIE's trainers to visit the CAS centres to deliver the training course. This surely inhibited participants' experiencing their ability to orient themselves autonomously in the local inclusion process and services during the training activities, but ensured continuity to the participants. Methods and activities had to be adjusted and reduced in time and intensity, the level of interaction between the HVG and the hosting community was consistently limited.

3.6 Core results of the TAIS implementation and potential impact on beneficiaries

Main outcome (intangible results) includes the novelty tool / methodology developed by CESIE, that proposes a bottom-up and participatory approach in education, shifting from INDUCED approach training offer to a SELECTIVE

one, allowing adult learners to increase their decision-making capacity by having direct influence over their learning path's content and modalities according to a set of individual variables (interests and aspirations, level of studies and previously attended programmes, logistics, and time availability, etc.).

Main outputs (tangible results) to be further developed and exploited by the ARU and wider Community of Users are:

"ALL you can LEARN" Digital Learning MENU

<https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/learn> for FDP and other vulnerable profiles.

The bilingual online selection tool (Italian and English) represents the digital "learning menu" that supports the testing of the TAIS SELECTIVE approach: trainees choose their learning path; digital users can cross select between different areas of knowledge/challenges to be achieved during the overall "ALL you can LEARN" training experience. Through a group code, participants access the online tool and are approached 'just' as adult learners with no indication of names or titles to their vulnerabilities.

"Create your Training Menu by choosing the learning objectives you want to achieve, demonstrating that adult education can play a key role, through its transformative possibilities and the power of the joy of learning. Everyone should have the right and the opportunity to access the adult education system - it is a common and public good and it transforms lives and societies to be more inclusive!"

Educational Resources for Professionals in the field of MIGRATION

<https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/teach/> for ARU/Observatory and Community of Users.

The RAISD Resource Database for professionals in education addressing the need for inclusive learning environments with special attention to distinctively Vulnerable Groups among the Forcibly Displaced and migrant communities in Europe. The learning materials support creative skills in education for youth, adults, vocational education and training, school communities as well as in Higher Education – supporting guidance, training, and teaching material with a focus on different methodologies tailored to specific target group segments and contexts of vulnerability."

Impact of the TAIS

The opportunity to work inside the CAS centre and to cooperate with the managers of the facility made a highly positive and performing impact possible. All women improved their decision-making skills and felt involved. Participants underlined how this cooperation mode made them feel like the authors of their own personal and professional growth project, learning new transversal skills but also growing in terms of language and knowledge of the territory in which they live. It was unanimously stated by the participants that the activities carried out in a moment of isolation (due to COVID-19 and its general restrictions) gave them hope for the future. In addition, all activities were supported by technological equipment brought into the centre by CESIE, such as laptops and tablets. This made the participants' technological skills grow vertically and progressively and increased their curiosity and active participation during all the sessions.

As stated by the first testimony of the Italian ARU Stories comes from Mr. Giuseppe Spinelli, an educator of the Freedom centre, a centre working with trafficked women. CESIE partnered with "[Cooperativa Nuova Generazione](#),

Freedom centre” in the nearby town of Trabia (20 km distance from Palermo) to implement the TAIS, contributing to the integration and inclusion of the vulnerable women arriving to the centre by arranging training sessions with and for them. A strength of the Italian ARU has been working on the territory and collaborating with different stakeholders, putting in place a network of operators from different fields to achieve the highest impact on the beneficiaries. Giuseppe highlights in his testimony the great enthusiasm and satisfaction of the young women for the opportunity offered by CESIE, and the participation in the training session was indeed massive. Among the main strengths of the TAIS and the work of the ARU, he noticed the capacity to break down the cultural and language barriers, and the ability of making the training highly interactive, engaging the participating women not only in the learning as such but also involving them emotionally, paying attention to their feelings during the process. The testimony is available here: <https://youtu.be/D-ALH805j7I>

The second testimonial of the Italian ARU Stories is Ms. Luigia Sunseri, one of the educators of the Freedom centre. During her interview, she immediately highlighted the importance of having the training delivered directly by CESIE at the centre. That was a key element for the girls hosted in the centre, increasing their feelings of confidence, security, protection, and wellbeing. Noteworthy was the great capacity on behalf of CESIE to involve the young women in the training, raising their curiosity and providing them with support in their path to the future. The hands-on part of the training was essential to match wishes and expectations with actual possibilities and competences. The initiative jointly delivered by CESIE and the Freedom centre was indeed a success for the inclusion and integration of the women, also looking at the long-term perspective it may open for them, towards a new independent space for their own lives. At the very end of her intervention, Luigia stressed the constructive and fruitful collaboration put in place with CESIE, that the centre welcomed very positively, and will be ready to welcome in the future as well. The testimony is available here: <https://youtu.be/NnpSma553as>

3.7 Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the ARUs' activities.

The co-authored design process had started about when the first COVID-19 lockdown in Italy come into force (March–May 2020); activities with piloting group 1 (18 participants) came to a stop during the new COVID-19 outbreak, with strict social encounter limitations, and the need for adjustments to video sessions (November 2020–January 2021); activities with piloting group 2 (9 participants) could be finalised by reducing the number of in-presence training hours (April–September 2021).

COVID-19 affected consistently the hosting of trainees at CESIE's training facilities (group 1) and the piloting within the CAS centres where trainees were actually living with their children (group 2). The impact of COVID-19 and social distancing regulations has meant that meetings with piloting group 1 were no longer face-to-face but at a distance. The first piloting participants were consulted individually to ask whether they agreed to switch to online modalities and if they would have available a digital device and internet connection to be able to continue with the activities, at least for the first part of the orientation sessions. The majority agreed, but actual results showed that the women did not have the necessary skills to use digital tools for distance education and the equipment used (smartphones mainly) was not adequate; therefore, the piloting of Group 1 came to a halt in December 2021.

Online support measures have been integrated to help learners in transitioning to distance learning [IT and EN]:

- a) Active citizenship and democracy <https://forms.gle/xCHLzvGohC5CH9PEA>
- b) Digitalisation <https://forms.gle/bLzGsf9vrAvuAMmJ7>
- c) Life skills <https://forms.gle/8b6YPA2vc8EHasyJ7>
- d) Health and wellbeing <https://forms.gle/tcQWU9KYKWQEj95L8>
- e) Social cohesion, equity, and equality <https://forms.gle/x9hvGHC8udwqoeDq6>
- f) Inclusive societies and cultures <https://forms.gle/hm2LAC2KuvJahG5X9>
- g) Employment and work <https://forms.gle/X9cxwxFrRhubS1CRA>

During the first COVID-19 lockdown period, there was a forced increase of distance learning methods and approaches, that found professionals in education unprepared in the delivery modes and knowledge multiplication. Therefore, despite all challenges, a specific request was to also establish a Resource Database for this secondary target group. It was a positive unexpected result revealed during the COVID-19 period: as there was a forced increase of distance learning methods and approaches targeting pupils and trainees, ARU members found professionals in education unprepared with the digital delivery modes and knowledge multiplication – therefore, it was a specific stakeholder request to offer a Resource Database for ARU members and the wider educational knowledge communities (Community of Users), where to seek guidance, training and teaching material with focus on topics related to migration and various inclusive methodologies for different types of HVG and degrees of vulnerability. <https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/teach/>

As a final outcome of the pandemic, the learning materials developed served to increase VG knowledge but also to support creative skills in education for youth, adults, vocational education and training, school communities as well as trainers and professionals. Find guidance, training and teaching material with a focus on different methodologies tailored to specific target group segments and contexts of vulnerability, with a total of currently 161 educational resources available to the Italian ARU and Community of Users.

3.8 Sustainability of the ARUs work after the project ends. How to keep them alive

The ARU will continue working on the research question, raised after the literature, policy review, interviews, and pilot activities: What are the most effective educational inclusion strategies for increasing participation and continuity in education among highly vulnerable displaced people currently living in the region of Sicily? The AUCL Strategy and its online infrastructure will continue operating after the end of the project as the ARU aims to further target-tailor and enhance the Learning Objectives to select from, increment the number of users and diversify HVG profiles that can benefit from it. In this sense, the ARU intends to continue operating after the end of the RAISD project, willing to increase the offers (and training offer) for vulnerable girls and women to select from, increase the number of users and diversify HVG profiles that can benefit from it. Given the flexible nature of TAIS, all thematic units are encouraged to use the tool with their own specific target groups, and this will in turn encourage transferability and sustainability of the TAIS.

To contribute to the future of the RAISD project, the ARU Observatory will allow for discussion, sharing, multiplication and transferability of the innovative concept at regional and national level. The AUCL (Italian TAIS) is expected to (a) generate genuine and sustainable improvements in the Learning and Training Environments (formal and non-formal)

and (b) improve the situation of Highly Vulnerable target groups regarding educational attainment, social inclusion and well-being. The TAIS ensures sustainability as the [AUCL Platform](#) is based on CESIE's server, thus its updating and maintenance will not require additional funding resources at the end of RAISD's project lifetime. Moreover, the tool allows adopting and adapting knowledge resources that have been developed and approved within European project context in many years of activity.

4 The Finnish ARU - the work of the University of Helsinki

4.1 Building of the ARU

The core team of the Finnish ARU, led by the University of Helsinki, was established in a meeting in September 2019. However, before that, during summer 2019 eight focus group meetings with 55 potential ARU members were arranged in different localities. ARU members in more local levels have been recruited during spring 2020.

As an institution, University of Helsinki does not have established contacts to the professional fields of so-called frontline workers (contrary to some specialised research institutes in Finland). Therefore, most contacts to potential ARU members have been created from scratch. However, Finland is a small country in terms of population and the public sector is quite centralised. It was thus rather easy to figure out possible members and potential experts for the Finnish ARU even though it was not possible to include all the helixes, this was mostly because 1. the lack of connections with the private sector and 2. the closed nature of the Finnish reception system dominated by officials and NGOs.

A quite distinct challenge in the process of starting the Finnish ARU was the language issue. The public and third sector experts even on refugee and FDP matters tend to be white Finnish-speaking majority not skilled in languages of the FDP. Consequently, as one of the first steps in setting up the ARU, there was a need to find people who could master Arabic and Dari/Farsi (most common languages among FDP in Finland), as well as English or Finnish. The solution was to recruit two subcontracts as research assistants.

A further challenge in forming the ARU was the multi-sited and two-fold approach of the Finnish sub-project. The aim is to promote two TAIS in various reception centres. The first one, a **Multilingual Online Forum** for asylum seeking and Finnish-speaking men, is piloted with men from several reception centres and with the help of many professionals. The second, instead, is devoted to **childcare activities developed in the context of two reception centres**.

Thus, the composition of the Finnish ARU is not fixed as different people are involved in developing, implementing, and evaluating different activities.

The core group of the Finnish ARU consists of project researchers (Antti Kivijärvi and Martta Myllylä), two subcontracted research assistants (Fairuz Muthana and Pargol Miraftabi) and one expert in the Finnish Red Cross (Hanna-Leena Tikkanen). In local levels and levels of practical implementation, ARU includes professionals working in several reception centres. In addition to experts in childcare activities, language tuition and online work, the ARU includes managers of two reception centres. Besides the RAISD team, no further employees of the University of Helsinki have been connected to the ARU so far.

The Finnish reception system is a highly separate institution. Mostly because of this fact, there have been difficulties in including a wide array of stakeholders. Mostly, the ARU leader dealt with civil society organisations, practically with Finnish Red Cross – workers, leaders, and experts. Other fields are included, not in the ARU, but for instance in the national steering committee.

For the TAIS (Pilot 1) Multilingual Online Forum the key are FDP men, individual volunteers, and Red Cross workers. The first two groups were deeply involved with the forum and developing it throughout its trajectory. Red Cross workers and experts had more of a supporting role in recruiting participants and being people with whom project workers could reflect any issue related to the TAIS.

For the TAIS (Pilot 2) development of child-care services in reception centres the key stakeholders are reception centre professionals and asylum-seeking parents. Thus, due to adjustment related to the pandemic, the TAIS succeeded better in involving the professionals, while remote involvement of asylum seekers was more difficult.

4.2 ARUs' way of working: meetings, exchanges, and decision-making process

Only the core team have been systematically involved since September 2019 due to the multi-sited and two-fold nature of the Finnish sub-project. ARU members with a more specific expertise have been invited after the focus of the pilots became more accurate.

All the meetings have been arranged in either the facilities of the University of Helsinki or in various reception centres. Moreover, due to the multi-sited approach, several phone, online meetings and interviews have been arranged as well. Obviously, the role of online meetings has drastically increased after the break of COVID-19 pandemic. Since March 2020, all communications among the ARU members have taken place in online systems or via email and phone calls.

Due to the multi-sited and participatory approach, as much leeway as possible have been given to the stakeholders to decide whether to include themselves to the project or not and whether to contribute to the project design. The aim of the first stakeholder meetings were mostly to probe the stakeholders' ideas. However, since the beginning of the year 2020, the activities and working of the ARU were more structured and pre-planned.

For the TAIS (Pilot 1) **Multilingual Online forum** all ARU meetings took place in online surroundings. To some extent, this would have probably been the case even without COVID-19, since ARU members lived in various regions of Finland. A project researcher coordinated all the ARU meetings. Some meetings took place with Red Cross workers while planning the TAIS and preparing the recruitment process. Other types of meetings involved peer moderators and volunteers while the aim was to discuss the practicalities of the forum, its development and the living conditions of asylum seekers in Finland.

For the TAIS (Pilot 2) (**development of child-care services in reception centres**) the first ARU meetings with the research group - two researchers and two research assistants - were face-to-face meetings. When the meetings with professionals of the two reception centres started, the COVID-19 pandemic was on, and meetings were organised online via Zoom. The distances in Finland are long and the co-operative reception centres are situated far from Helsinki in which the members of the research team were mainly living. Therefore, the meeting practices typical in the pandemic situation were actually economical and useful. Even though the goals of the meetings were reached via online meetings, a few more face-to-face- meetings could have been supporting the co-operation even more. In addition to face-to-face and online meetings, there were discussions among the ARU members via e-mails and phone calls.

4.3 How were the TAIS defined by the ARU members

According to the Vulnerable Group identified in Finland, two Pilots, as previously said, were launched by the ARU.

The first TAIS (Pilot 1) Multilingual Online forum was primarily targeted to young and single asylum-seeking men who are rarely seen to be in a vulnerable position in the context of public and even academic discussions on refugees and forced displacement. The popular notion of vulnerability tends to put young asylum-seeking men in a category of non-deserving and even dangerous migrants. However, many asylum-seeking young men miss the support of their families, are treated as adults in the asylum process and reception system and are susceptible to discrimination and labour market exploitation and lack targeted services. More specifically, young asylum-seeking men lack the opportunities to use and learn everyday language with Finnish-speaking peers. Most of the contacts they have with Finnish-speakers are elderly women since they tend to volunteer through NGOs. Particularly in smaller towns and rural areas there are few possibilities in contacting Finnish-speaking young people. Moreover, according to several asylum seeker interviews, the language tuition within the reception centres is not enough, takes place only in classrooms and is too repetitive due to constantly changing teachers and learners and the huge diversity of educational backgrounds different asylum seekers have. Several of the interviewed asylum-seeking men pointed to a need to be introduced to everyday life, language, and culture in Finland. Moreover, many of them missed information about the labour market, education system and various possibilities in Finland.

The online forum was adjusted to fit the needs of a specific sub-group of asylum seekers from the very beginning when designing the TAIS. Moreover, and quite importantly, the forum was implemented and developed in three cycles during 2020 and 2021. During the cycles, several adjustments were made according to feedback received from asylum seekers, Finnish-speaking volunteers and recruiting professionals. For instance, these adjustments included manoeuvres such as revising the invitation letter (more simple language and the aim of the forum more clearly described), recruiting peer moderators, stressing topics related to practical information and knowledge on Finnish society and including an introductory training for peer moderators and volunteers before the start of the forum. Moreover, and quite importantly, there was a constant need of finding ways of communicating in simple and concrete language and using various images to increase mutual understanding.

The second TAIS (Pilot 2) concerns instead the development of child-care services in reception centres. The contextual vulnerability was identified based on interviews of both reception centre professionals and asylum-seekers in the first stage of the project. At first, in the focus-group interviews of workers of seven Finnish Red Cross (FRC) reception centres in different parts of Finland, a difficult situation of families with small children was highlighted. Guided by this notion, asylum-seeking parents with small children (n=11, six mothers and five fathers) were chosen to be interviewed to deepen the understanding of their situation and to investigate their needs further. The lack and need of child-care services for asylum-seeking families were identified based on these interviews.

Asylum-seeking parents of small children, particularly single parents, suffer from a lack of child-care services while trying to cope in highly stressful conditions. In most Finnish regions and with very few exceptions, asylum-seeking families have no right to early childhood education in municipal day-care centres. Asylum seeking children are entitled to enter the Finnish education system in pre-school at the age of six. Moreover, reception centres are not obligated to provide child-care and, therefore, the level of provided activities varies significantly between different

reception centres. Some centres do not organise childcare services at all while, at best, some centres provide help in child-care for a few hours per week.

For many families, this type of context tends to cause problems or aggravate already existing ones. Parents have difficulties in using the services they are entitled to and their abilities to work or educate themselves and rest are highly limited. Children miss structured activities with their peers and their learning and integration into Finnish society are severely hampered.

From the very beginning, informed by the interviews above mentioned, the TAIS was targeted to meet specific group-level needs of the parents of small children by developing child-care services in reception centres. In the three pilot cycles, more individual needs were considered by collecting feedback through face-to-face and remote (phone calls and video meetings) discussions and interviews with professionals and parents and participatory observation of provided child-care services. From the knowledge acquired, both qualitative and quantitative targets of development were identified, and this feedback was communicated to reception professionals working with child-care services through many meetings and training sessions.

The first cycle focused on creating a comprehensive picture of the child-care services and needs for development. In the second cycle, the focus was on qualitative improvements of the services. After gathering and analysing qualitative data on the material, cultural and social conditions of the child-care services, the ARU identified good practices and targets of development in the service's premises, structure and contents. While the main deficiency of the child-care services, according to parents, was the insufficient number of services, the third cycle consisted of a trial of more intensive child-care in one reception centre.

In addition to improving the services in one centre, a focal part of the tailoring process was to benchmark the best practices and document them to create a model for child-care services in reception centres in Finland and in general. Moreover, knowledge collected in the TAIS will be used to show how asylum-seeking children's access to daily day-care, and in the best case, in municipal early childhood education and care services would meet asylum-seeking families' needs.

4.4 How the ARUs started working with their TAIS, and who implemented it

Multilingual Online forum TAIS (Pilot 1) was mainly provided by the RAISD-project researchers and Red Cross voluntary workers. The moderation of the discussions was a responsibility of a project researcher. The need for contributions from reception centre professionals or particularly other stakeholders was modest. Reception centres and their professionals helped in recruiting asylum seeking men. Moreover, they were encouraged to help asylum seeking men, if necessary, in writing their posts or reading others' writings. Finnish-speaking volunteers were recruited with the help of an expert working in the central office of The Finnish Red Cross. She is responsible for developing the offline and particularly online volunteer work in their organisation. There has been no need for completely new collaborators to carry out the latest rounds of TAIS. However, there has been a need to invite some of the asylum seekers to adopt new types of roles in the forum. This has meant engaging them as peer moderators instead of only participants. This has encouraged them to be more active in the forum and help other participants to express their ideas in different languages.

Table 3: Profile of TAIS implementers. Finland 1

Profile of TAIS implementers					
<u>Total number:</u>		Female:	14	Male:	5
Number of research staff:		Female:	2	Male:	1
Number of administrative:		Female:	10	Male:	3
Number of training experts:		Female:	1	Male:	1
Number of technical staff:		Female:	1	Male:	

The main principle in the TAIS 2 of the Finnish ARU has been the involvement of key stakeholders in the process of designing the TAIS, referring particularly to asylum seekers and reception centre professionals. Since the Finnish reception system is a highly segregated institution, legislatively and administratively isolated from other public bodies and societal sectors, the inclusion of stakeholders such as municipal authorities, several NGOs and private companies has been somewhat difficult.

However, in the second round, the public sector was involved as a new type of collaborator. Based on the interviews carried out in the first round, a key aspiration of the asylum-seeking parents was to get their children into municipal day-care centres. Moreover, the information gathering in the first round showed municipalities applying very varying practices in asylum seekers' access to day-care services. Therefore, municipal officials and workers responsible for municipal day-care services were interviewed to discover the roots of varying practices of municipalities.

Table 4: Profile of TAIS implementers. Finland 2

Profile of TAIS implementers					
<u>Total number:</u>	12	Female:	9	Male:	3
Number of research staff:	4	Female:	3	Male:	1
Number of administrative:	2	Female:	1	Male:	1
Number of training experts:	-	Female:	-	Male:	-
Number of technical staff:	6	Female:	5	Male:	1

4.5 What was good and what went wrong in the TAIS

4.5.1 TAIS (Pilot 1) Multilingual Online forum

From the perspective of service providers, the Multilingual Online forum clearly has plenty of potential in success due to its viability. Setting up a forum and moderating it has not required large amounts of working hours or specific skills. Probably the main requirement for the main moderator is knowledge on the migration related issues and quite detailed awareness about the rights and living conditions of asylum seekers. On the other hand, if the moderator already has this type of knowledge, his/her competence is not likely to increase to great extent.

As for the beneficiaries, there have been indications of some successes as well. The evaluation is still in progress and further elements, successful and/or unsuccessful, will be available in the future.

Successful elements

Accessibility

The forum is quite accessible and only in rare cases there have been problems in reaching the platform.

Empowerment and Non-discrimination

For some asylum seekers, the forum has been accepted and intensively used which has occasionally meant also potential for empowerment in the form of being able to practice written language, being accepted by fellow discussants, and receiving knowledge about everyday life in Finland.

Inclusion

For some of the volunteers, the platform has revealed the everyday living conditions and interests of asylum seekers. It has thus had the potential to increase the trust between the two social categories quite far from each other. Volunteers had no previous personal contacts with asylum seekers.

Unsuccessful elements and/or unexpected limitations

Reduction in the beneficiaries number

From the perspective of the service provider, probably the main unsuccessful element was the recruitment process. The number of both asylum seekers and voluntary workers was too modest. The relatively low number of people (from ten to twenty) in any online forum increases the risk of silence and passivity. In this sense, the accessibility of the forum could have been better.

Lack of a more concrete and long-term perspective

Moreover, in terms of acceptability, the forum lacked clearly articulated and concrete benefits for the participants. The aim might have been too abstract for some asylum seekers while most of them are interested in finding places of study and work and concrete advice. Nationwide forums may not be able to do this since asylum seekers tend to live in more peripheral areas while volunteers are more familiar with situations in the few urban areas of Finland. Consequently, and from the perspective of outcome criteria, online forum is stronger in subjective goals related to inclusion and capability but weaker in enhancing the actual social bonds or employment opportunities.

Finally, since the online forum was a totally new endeavour in the context of Finnish reception services, there is an obvious risk of losing the results of the developmental work after the project resources are not there anymore. Consequently, there is no guarantee that the TAIS will continue to exist after the RAISD project. The Finnish Red Cross does not have the resources or structures to support the work.

4.5.2 TAIS (Pilot 2) Developing child-care services in reception centres

When developing already existing services, successful elements of the services themselves and successful elements of the developing activities need to be analysed separately. Thorough evaluation of accessibility, acceptability, empowerment and viability of child-care services in FRC reception from both service providers and beneficiaries' perspectives are presented in evaluation reports of the first and second cycle, based on information collected in the first two rounds. The TAIS had some successes in improving the identified unsuccessful elements of the current services.

Supposedly, the most tangible successes of the development of child-care services for the beneficiaries, asylum-seeking families, will appear during the trial of a more intensive period of child-care services in one centre. During the trial, parents are able to get more time to rest, study and run errands while their children get structured activities more regularly. This will increase the acceptability of the services as well as their empowering effects. Moreover, the accessibility will be improved by providing some lifts to the services that were physically hard to reach for some families living far in the context of missing public transport. Supposedly, parents' capabilities will be increased by increasing parents' autonomy when they get more time to be invested according to their own wishes, and the subjective wellbeing of both children and parents may increase. Inclusion may increase especially in cases in which parents use their time for education. TAIS may increase the capacities of the children by offering more intensive structures to improve their cognitive, motoric, language and socio-emotional skills and capacities of parents by providing a possibility to participate in language lessons.

Successful elements of the development of the child-care services to promote service providers' competence was to get feedback from parents and to take their perspective into account in the services, in addition to children's interest. In the centre in which the trial of more intensive child-care was carried out, professionals got more resources for child-care activities to both improve the contents as well as increase the amount of the services. In the best case from the service providers' perspective, the results and the documentation of the TAIS results will work as a justification for getting permanent funding for more intensive and improved child-care services in a reception centre. Finally, the written model will work as a guideline for the provision of viable child-care services in other reception centres.

When developing already existing services, unsuccessful elements of the services themselves and unsuccessful elements of developing activities need to be analysed separately. Thorough evaluation of accessibility, acceptability, empowerment and viability of child-care services in FRC reception centres reception from both service providers and beneficiaries' perspectives have been drafted based on information collected in the first two rounds evaluation reports.

Accessibility

Access to services is difficult for many families who live far from the premises in which child-care is organised, while public transportation is rare or missing. There is no child-care available for children under 2 or 3 years.

Acceptability

The main deficiency of the services is the insufficient hours of child-care.

Empowerment

Multi-lingual clubs without Finnish-speaking peers do not promote children's language skills. Some parents call for more concrete and material support instead of professionals' focus on parenting advice sometimes experienced as patronising.

Viability

Constant changes in the field of asylum seekers' reception (decreased funding, moving from one premise to another) hinder the provision of high-quality and stable services.

Supposedly, from both service providers' and beneficiaries' perspectives, the most unsuccessful element of the developing activities would be the non-recurrence of the period of more intensive child-care services, if the funding could not be ensured from other sources. For beneficiaries, this would mean a reduction of the services and a decrease in lifts from the service premises after the trial. Service providers, in turn, would need to explain and justify the reduction of the services for beneficiaries and to motivate them to still participate in the services, while their own resources to provide the services would have decreased. Goals related to outcome criteria as increasing capabilities and inclusion, and improving capacities as promotion of language skills, require long-term perspective and activities and are not reached in a short period of more intensive services.

Moreover, when developing already existing services, the structures, culture, and workings of the institution (reception centres and reception system more widely) frame the possibilities of improvements. In the process, it became visible how parents' and professionals' views on families' needs were not always consistent. For instance, parents experienced bringing and taking children to/from child-care services hard (*accessibility*), while the workers saw it as an act of activation (*empowerment*). Moreover, while parents wished for more autonomy to choose their actions during child-care services, the service providers called for educating activities. In these cases, the concrete solutions (the amount of lifts; the share of free time and educational activities to parents) had to be negotiated and compromised.

4.6 Core results of the TAIS implementation and potential impact on beneficiaries

Through the **TAIS (Pilot 1) Multilingual Online forum**, the aim was to promote the inclusion and capacities of asylum-seeking men. In this case, inclusion refers to increased trust between asylum-seeking and Finnish-speaking men and lowered threshold in approaching each other. As for the capacities, the aim was to improve asylum seekers' skills in everyday written language and lower the threshold in using it. Moreover, capacities refer to increased knowledge of

Finnish culture and institutions. Further, for Finnish-speaking men improved capacities refer to increased knowledge and understanding of the rights and living conditions of asylum seekers in Finland.

The outcome evaluation is still in process and a more complete overview is not available yet. However, one can assume that not all the goals will be met. One of the setbacks was the limited number of participants – the potential impact could have been wider. Moreover, as with almost all interventions in the social spheres of human action, the impacts (if there are any) are probably quite modest and not necessarily seen in the outcome measures.

No unexpected negative or positive impacts have been observed.

Impact of the TAIS (Pilot 1)

Through the testimonials collected in the ARU stories (D.7.1), it is possible to report a positive experience as told by Stephen Oppong, a young man from Ghana, who participated in the Finnish ARU, at first as final beneficiary and then as a moderator to help further young men, asylum seekers, who have arrived in Finland.

Stephen is the direct testimonial that the Multilingual Online groups for young men have had a positive end. He arrived in Finland two years ago. He heard of the RAISD project while he was living in a refugee camp. He was at first a final beneficiary, using the forum to get information. Information such as being enrolled in schools, the kind of information, he said, it was not easy to reach out by staying in a camp. Since last August he is not living in a refugee camp anymore, he works, and he is married now. Stephen is currently participating in the Multilingual Online groups for young men, as a moderator and trying to help other young men that are experiencing the same path he went through. His contribution is available in the [ARU stories](#).

Through the TAIS (Pilot 2), the aim was to promote the well-being of asylum-seeking families. For parents, access to child-care services enables them to invest time in various activities, use of services, studying and rest. Consequently, the potential outcome of the pilot would be decreased levels of stress and anxiety and increased subjective well-being. Moreover, the TAIS would possibly increase parents' autonomy while they have free time they can use how they wish. Also, inclusion and capacities may increase while parents can invest their time in studying. Obviously, participating in good-quality childcare activities has the potential to foster the well-being and learning of children, and alleviate the possible anxieties of children stemming from forced displacement.

The outcome evaluation is still in process, and it is not yet complete the results' overview. Probably, the trial will have a positive impact on the parent while it is going on, but it is harder to evaluate long-term impacts. However, as with almost all interventions in the social spheres of human action, the impacts (if there are any) are probably quite modest and not necessarily seen in the outcome measures.

A positive impact related to service providers is their enthusiasm towards the development work, as they are trying to keep the more intensive structure of the child-care services after the trial period via other funding sources. A negative impact may be service providers' tendency to bind child-care activities to parents' activities happening in the meantime, while the parents wish to get more free time in addition to the chance to take part in the study and other activities.

Impact of the TAIS (Pilot 2)

Through the testimonials collected in the ARU stories (D.7.1) the director of the Rovaniemi Reception Centre, a small city in Northern Finland and the assistant manager and a physiotherapist of the Kristiinankaupunki Reception Centre, in Western Finland, both centres part of the Finnish Red Cross, have shared their experience as stakeholders within the ARU and the importance to have been involved in the ARU to reflect on the improvement of the activities already carried on in the reception centres. Their full testimonials are available in the [ARU stories](#).

4.7 Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the ARUs' activities

Besides the way of organisations of meetings already reported in the section "ARUs' way of working: meetings, exchanges and decision-making process", COVID-19 pandemic impacted on both TAIS activities.

COVID-19 pandemic affected the implementation of the **TAIS (Pilot 1) Multilingual Online forum** in both direct and indirect ways. Probably the biggest impact has been indirect. Due to the pandemic, European borders have been even more closed than in previous years and mobilities of forcibly displaced people have been reduced to a minimum. At the start of the Pandemic in Europe in early 2020, Finnish reception centres hosted thousands of asylum seekers who arrived in 2015 and 2016. After that, only a few asylum seekers had been able to arrive in Finland due to several restrictions in European immigration policies. All this has meant that, in 2020 and 2021, Finnish reception centres have been inhabited by asylum seekers who suffer from protracted waiting in uncertainty. This is manifested in reduced mental health, unwillingness to participate in offered activities and despair. Consequently, at the time we have been trying to recruit participants in a novel and inclusive trial, reception centres have been inhabited by a reduced number of asylum seekers lacking motivation.

Furthermore, another indirect impact of the pandemic was related to reception centre professionals and their number and motivation to engage in developmental work. As a result of decreasing number of asylum seekers, the Finnish ARU has witnessed shutdowns of several reception centres, reduced number of personnel and several uncertainties in the whole industry. These conditions have probably hampered the willingness and eagerness of reception centres and their workers to invest time in extra tasks such as co-operating with external projects. People have been more interested in their future and maintaining their positions in a sector in turbulence.

In addition to indirect consequences, there have been several direct impacts as well. One of them has obviously been social distancing. Even though the online forum does not require face-to-face activities, they would be beneficial in trust building and in recruitment. Due to restrictive measures, the Finnish ARU leaders were not able to meet reception centre professionals and get to know them in the level that would have increased their understanding of the TAIS and the ideas behind it. Further, in many cases, reception centre professionals were not able to meet asylum seekers in person to let them know about the possibility of participating in the forum.

All these COVID-19 related issues have been quite severe and there are no simple solutions to deal with them. The only solutions have been constant efforts to build online connections and trust, resorting to familiar people (who were met before the lockdown measures) and putting a lot of effort in clear communication.

The COVID-19 pandemic impacts on the **TAIS (Pilot 2) development of child-care services** were, as well, direct and indirect. The direct impact was related to social distancing policies that affected both provision of child-care services

and researchers' physical access to reception centres. Because of the restrictive measures, the whole first cycle was implemented from a distance by conducting remote interviews with asylum-seeking parents and e-surveying reception centre professionals. In one centre, all clubs for children were suspended for over a year from spring 2020 to spring 2021. At first, clubs were closed because of the pandemic, when schools and day-care centres were partly closed in the whole country to decrease infections. Moreover, the break in the services persisted due to bureaucratic problems in renovating the new premises to meet required safety standards. Closed clubs were replaced by home-delivered activity bundles that included games, toys, and crafting materials with instructions. In the second cycle in autumn 2020, a planned visit to the centre to observe these alternative activities was cancelled due to a worsening pandemic situation. Information was, therefore, gathered by video-interview with the professionals. In another centre, clubs were occasionally available apart from the pandemic and a visit was carried out in autumn 2020. However, parents reported a distinct decrease in the provision of activities.

Moreover, and as indicated for the TAIS (Pilot 1) there were indirect impacts related to the amount of asylum seekers in reception centres in Finland. Due to the pandemic, European borders have been even more closed than in previous years and mobilities of forcibly displaced people have been reduced to a minimum. At the start of the pandemic in Europe in early 2020, Finnish reception centres hosted thousands of asylum seekers who arrived in 2015 and 2016. After that, only a few asylum seekers had been able to arrive in Finland due to several restrictions in European immigration policies. Consequently, when it was finally time to implement the third round, the trial of more intensive child-care services, there were no families with small children in one of the centres: the previous asylum seekers had got their decisions and moved away from the centre, while there were no new families accommodated. This centre, therefore, withdrew from the TAIS and the trial was implemented in one centre only.

The solutions for data gathering in the time of social distancing (video and phone interviews and an e-survey) were able to produce certain kinds of information from the services. However, more ethnographic observation while being physically present was needed in order to create a coherent picture of the services. Visits were carried out in the second and third rounds. While the withdrawal of one of the centres was a regrettable turn, we were able to invest more for the trial of the remaining centre.

4.8 Sustainability of the ARUs' work after the project ends. How to keep them alive

The sustainability of the ARU work for the Multilingual Online forum after the project ends is definitely a challenge. Online forum was something totally new in the Finnish reception system, missing permanent resources and structures to guarantee its sustainability. There have been some discussions related to sustainability with an online expert and an FDP expert working in the central office of Finnish Red Cross. The main thing to do, is to document the TAIS in the best way possible and make it clear that it is quite easy to be implemented in the future. The aim has been to introduce the idea to the right people in the Finnish Red Cross and push them to see the feasibility and the potential in it. It is a new channel to recruit and engage male volunteers which has been an enduring problem for the Red Cross for decades. Further, online forum offers a light way of volunteer work not requiring lots of invested time or long-term commitments. Consequently, online forum is one potential answer to the problem of decreasing NGO participation rate in Finland.

In the RAISD project, the online forum was implemented during times not favourable to the TAIS. Closed borders, decreasing number of asylum seekers and their declining mental condition and lack of motivation probably hampered recruitment of beneficiaries to a great extent. Therefore, one can expect that there would be much more demand for this type of method after the migration flows reach the levels prior to the pandemic.

For the development of child-care services in the reception centres – Pilot 2, the elements hindering sustainability are related to the shortness of the trial of more intensive childcare services. However, the TAIS also had elements supporting future sustainability.

Firstly, even though the amount of the services would decrease back to the level they were before the trial in the cooperative reception centre, the services will not entirely finish. The qualitative improvement of the services carried out during the development process will sustain in ongoing child-care services of the reception centre. Moreover, the reception centre now has the experience and model of providing more intensive child-care services, thus, they can be easily widened if the resources increase again in the future. Actually, the reception centre is hoping for the trial and the documentation of the development work and its results to justify more stable provision on more intensive child-care.

Secondly, the model of child-care services established in the project can be used in reception centres throughout Finland. The modelling will help the coordinating authorities (The Finnish Migration Service and The Finnish Red Cross) and other local actors (reception centres) to implement quality child-care services in other settings as well.

Thirdly, the outcome of the TAIS proves the importance and advantage of regular child-care services for asylum-seeking families. These results can be used in advocacy work to argue for more regular child-care services in reception centres and/or for guaranteeing asylum-seeking children's access to municipal early childhood and care services.

5 The Hungarian ARU - the work of the Menedék Association

5.1 Building of the ARU

According to the Guidebook developed by UNIMED at the beginning of the RAISD project, Menedék – Hungarian Association for Migrants, leader of the Hungarian ARU, started to structure the ARU. Having a wide network of practitioners and researchers in the field of migration, for Menedék was rather easy to draft a list of possible ARU members, except for government actors, due to the attitude of the current government towards the forced migration.

Besides the staff members involved in the project management from the start, it was an important principle that different professional skills should be represented, covering the broadest possible range of Menedék's activities. For this reason, besides the staff members involved in management, ARU meetings were visited, since the beginning, also by Menedék's colleagues with a considerable expertise in social work, child protection, trainings and education, legal help, and policy analysis.

In the conceptualisation of the ARU, a key question was whether refugees and stakeholders could work together in meetings that deal with the topic on a higher level of abstraction, not on the level of individual experiences. As an example, it was mentioned that a PTSD patient and a psychologist could work well on a specific traumatic event in the framework of a therapy, but not necessarily in the framework of an ARU meeting. Therefore, ARU was conceived as an essentially stakeholder-focused working group. (Another mechanism was introduced to involve refugees as reported in the second section "ARUs' way of working: meetings, exchanges and decision-making process"). Another more practical question was the language to be used at the meetings. It would have been beneficial to have meetings in English besides (or instead of) Hungarian from the perspective of including foreigners. Yet, it would have had the negative effect of discouraging Hungarian speakers who are not sufficiently fluent in English. Finally, Hungarian was chosen to be the language of the ARU meetings.

Concerning the aspect indicated in the Guidebook to have representatives of the quintuple helix, NGO and academia was easy to reach. It was difficult to involve representatives of business entities, as well as representatives of central government bodies, for two main reasons. First, employers usually do not employ a large number of refugees. Second, due to the anti-refugee propaganda of the government, central institutions as well as business leaders were not open to collaboration. Menedék tried, however, to involve local government representatives and business sector representatives with whom Menedék had ties due to another project about labour market insertion.

5.2 ARUs' way of working: meetings, exchanges, and decision-making process

May 2019 was the date of the internal setup of the ARU (within Menedék's team), while the first ARU meeting took place on 16 July 2019. Since then, two more ARU meetings were held, on 10 September 2019 and on 14 January 2020.

During the implementation period of the TAIS, Menedék organised the following ARU meetings:

- ARU meeting on 2 April 2020, discussing the interview analysis results, and the outcome of the best practice collection. Introducing the action plan for the following period.

- ARU meeting on 11 September 2020, discussing anonymised case descriptions and exploring the situation and the possibilities of action.
- ARU meeting on 16 March 2021, TAIS Round 2 results - reflections from the participating organisations.
- A “Train the trainers” session on 4 May 2021, for social workers of other organisations, based on the TAIS, sharing the concept of vulnerability and jointly showcasing training activities that address this topic.
- An enhanced ARU meeting on 26 May 2021 with new members, facilitating a conversation and reflections on the TAIS with intercultural mediators.
- Another enhanced ARU meeting on 11 October 2021 with new members, including local level service providers in related fields.

ARU members and invited participants of ARU meetings are affiliated to the following institutions: UNHCR (international organisation), IOM (international organisation), Terre des Hommes Foundation (international NGO), Amnesty International (international NGO), Directorate General of Aliens Policing (national policy maker), Family Support Centre - Budapest XIV (local policy maker), Family Support Centre - Győr (local policy maker), Károlyi István Centre for unaccompanied minors (local policy maker), Hungarian Helsinki Committee (NGO), Hungarian Baptist Aid (NGO), Cordelia Foundation (NGO), Diaconia of the Lutheran Church (NGO), Hungarian Evangelical Brotherhood (NGO), Jesuit Refugee Service (NGO), Next Step EU (NGO), She 4 She (NGO), Subjective Values Foundation (NGO), Artemisszió Foundation (NGO), Oltalom Caritative Association (NGO), Oltalom Sports Association (NGO), Ferencváros Community Foundation (NGO), Eötvös Loránd University (academia).

A total of 34 people (other than the core implementation team) participated in at least one ARU meeting, of which 21 were female and 13 were male.

Due to the confinement caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, the ARU meetings held between April 2020 and May 2021 were online. Furthermore, COVID-19 caused a loss of capacity at most of the ARU member institutions: transition to remote work was difficult for those who were working with refugees, given the limited access of this group to suitable electronic devices. Therefore, many service providers experienced an increase in their activities and had less time for participating at the meetings.

ARU meetings were usually moderated by a core TAIS implementation team member from Menedék. NGO representatives were stable and dedicated participants of the meetings. Feedback came usually from NGOs working directly with refugees. The feedback of ARU members was channelled into the work plan of the following period of the TAIS implementation. Almost all the foreseen members were involved since the beginning of the ARU. Only two or three of the invited members who wanted to join the meetings were not available on the dates scheduled. The activities were partially planned immediately. The big picture was clear from the start, yet it was usually only the next meeting's topic that was well defined when a given ARU meeting took place, i.e. it was possible to tell ARU members what the topic of the next meeting would be. Direct involvement of refugees in vulnerability contexts would have been difficult to arrange due to language and availability issues. Instead, the basic topics of RAISD (vulnerability concepts) were introduced to two other groups that are steered by Menedék's social workers, one for immigrant minors and one for immigrant women. Members gave their feedback and it was used in the decision-making process about the TAIS topic and layout. A further ARU meeting was conducted with refugee community leaders during the implementation period of the TAIS.

5.3 How were the TAIS defined by the ARU members

In Hungary, the weakness of institutions and inter-institutional coordination in the social sphere and the difficult access to many institutions and services have a negative effect on the vulnerability of the forcibly displaced. It is so because funding for such institutions is low, the political context is hostile, and the service providing structures are in a difficult situation. Therefore, many times the root of the problem is that a client with complex vulnerabilities could not receive support at the right place, at the right time. Many people fall out of the scope of supportive services because complex problems cannot be tackled by one service provider alone. Also, in many cases, the vulnerabilities or traumas are caused by the asylum system (or the lack thereof), as seen in the interviews detailing the horrors of the Balkan route or the shock of the Dublin procedure.

Most of the interviewed VG representatives could not identify properly (by name, service period, name of the organisation) specific programs designed for migrants or refugees. State-run programs are not visible since the engagement in the field of integration services between state institutions (the Immigration Office or the Family Support Centres) started to decrease, being finally eliminated in June 2018. Also, the similar or substitute services financed from the EU's Asylum, Migration, and Integration Fund, such as housing programs, language courses, labour market integration support, were phased out.

Furthermore, the analysis of the interviews made in 2019 showed that "coping mechanisms" are related to a "supporting environment" of the individual, which in turn can be divided into two fields: organic and institutional. Those who rely on an organic, supporting environment overcome the traumas and integration difficulties easier than those who cannot. For the latter group, it is necessary to develop an institutional environment where actors engage in non-formal, dynamic co-operation-based structures to improve the resilience of vulnerable individuals and groups.

Currently, the number of refugees in the mainstream service system is low. Service providers deal with many different aspects when working with these individuals. But not everyone has the opportunity to meet and talk to affected people.

Menedék has been dealing with refugees for more than twenty-five years and has encountered success stories and failures as well. There are similarities behind many different stories of refugees: resources, life paths, aggravating factors, various coping strategies, lucky encounters, dramatic coincidences. Menedék also knows that the "host society" often is not actually supportive and even rolls obstacles in front of a person. It is essential to recognise these contexts in which individual vulnerability can be interpreted in other dimensions.

In mapping the vulnerable context, Menedék distinguishes areas that can be interpreted separately yet collectively create vulnerable contexts:

- Personality, adaptation strategies that can influence the vulnerable situation in different directions. One can even deepen other elements of the context if, for example, someone has a low ability to adapt. The opposite can help the individual to overcome vulnerability faster and more effectively.
- The size and quality of the interpersonal and social network greatly influence whether vulnerability deepens and turns into a lasting crisis, such as when someone is facing long-term unemployment.
- The particular short- or long-term life situation may fundamentally and in itself presuppose the potential existence of a vulnerability context. Examples are the categories often used in the asylum system:

unaccompanied minors, single parents, people with disabilities, trauma survivors, victims of sexual abuse, people living in persistent poverty.

- The functioning of the legal environment and the social care system around us. In Hungary, a key question when examining the vulnerability contexts of refugees is what situations are caused by legal regulations or what are the responses of the social care system.

Due to the environment mentioned above, the TAIS was implemented on the meso level. The issues relating to poorly trained service providers who lack the right tools to engage with refugees were, therefore, the main targets of the Hungarian TAIS. Enhancing their knowledge and understanding of the various dimensions of vulnerability contexts and supporting their self-reflection could significantly impact the reduction of individuals' vulnerability. Also, operating at the meso level can result in sustainable results in the current hostile environment that characterises Hungary. The base and the principal field of application of this activity was individual social work with vulnerable refugees. However, every circle of the quintuple helix can benefit from profile and trajectory descriptions that contain the analysis of typical cases, a "vulnerability checklist" for clients and the intervention maps for vulnerability profiles. Also, on the service provider side, it was essential to consider the emotional burden on social workers. A personalised approach is more helpful for preventing "vicarisation," i.e. when emotional burden takes its toll on the social worker.

Menedék's research has also shown that vulnerable contexts can have recurring patterns and are interrelated. With these in mind, however, one must always approach it from the individual's point of view when interpreting a particular vulnerability. An example of this is that living alone or having a family can determine a vulnerable life situation in the same way, but both can be protective depending on the individual's current needs, circumstances, and context. Menedék's interviewees agreed that the protective role of the family is important, its lack makes them more vulnerable. However, Menedék also talked to people who became more vulnerable due to their family situation and status.

Based on the results of mapping the vulnerability contexts, Menedék concluded that service providers are playing a pivotal role in vulnerability reduction. To address the lack of self-reflection in the daily practices of service providers, Menedék built a new pilot program involving the social workers, service providers, and ARUs to develop a methodological system for self-reflection. These helpers must become aware that the dimensions in their work process, their way of communicating with clients can create new or increase the vulnerability of their clients.

The TAIS responded to the specific needs of vulnerable individuals but not directly instead as they manifest to the service providers during their interaction, therefore developing tools to enhance the efficiency and transparency in the relationship between the vulnerable individuals and helpers was crucial. To achieve this, self-reflection of the helpers about their daily practices was a key element.

5.4 How the ARUs started working with their TAIS, and who implemented it

There were two participatory roles in the TAIS activities. The direct participants were social workers and assisting professionals of relevant institutions and organisations (including ARU members but also representatives of other institutions). The beneficiaries (vulnerable individuals) participated indirectly through the interviews they have given to describe their case studies.

The coordination and facilitation of the TAIS activities were conducted by Menedék as the central actor. The external promoters were represented by ARU members whose contribution was significant for good communication and practices. Furthermore, over the project process, ARU member profiles have been expanded as Menedék invited representatives from the municipality and state levels. In the piloting phase, the range of colleagues involved in the self-reflection program has expanded. Menedék has included all colleagues who provide assistance to refugees within the association. Also, the number of participants during the workshops and trainings have changed according to the interest of other organisations members.

Three Rounds for the implementation of the piloting were conducted:

ROUND 1: from 15 May 2020 to 15 November 2020.

ROUND 2: from 15 November 2020 to 15 April 2021.

ROUND 3: from 15 April 2021 to 15 November 2021.

The TAIS in Hungary did not address vulnerable refugees directly. Instead, it addressed social workers and other professionals who are in daily contact with refugees. TAIS participants include social workers, professionals, and intercultural mediators of ARU members, as well as participants of the piloting of the “toolbox” undertaken in the third round of TAIS implementation. Most of them are affiliated to NGOs providing social assistance to foreigners in Hungary.

Table 5: Profile of TAIS implementers. Hungary

Profile of TAIS implementers					
Total number:	8	Female:	5	Male:	3
Number of research staff:	7	Female:	4	Male:	3
Number of administrative:	3	Female:	2	Male:	1
Number of training experts:	3	Female:	2	Male:	1
Number of technical staff:	0	Female:	0	Male:	0

5.5 What was good and what went wrong in the TAIS

Successful elements

The TAIS took place on the meso level and potentially affected the micro level. The emphasis was on the interpersonal and individual conditions of the beneficiaries: for social workers and other helpers, “reviewing” cases, reflecting on them brought professional deepening and the possibility of supervision.

In terms of the RAISD evaluation criteria, the following have been identified:

Accessibility

The low presence of refugees in Hungary impacted the number of service-providing institutions and organisations. During the TAIS development, the ARU was able to reach the majority of the refugee-specific organisations. These NGO members came from different hierarchical levels and became active creators of the project through the ARU. They brought in their diverse expertise and valuable inputs throughout the process. Furthermore, during the different stages of the TAIS, individuals with refugee backgrounds also participated in the ARU.

Acceptability

The beneficiaries of the TAIS reacted positively and actively participated in the piloting period. During the first phase, the social workers who wrote the case descriptions were cooperative and provided positive feedback about the writing process.

Empowerment

Menedék identified different levels of empowerment. Firstly, social workers became more knowledgeable about the vulnerability contexts and have gained valuable experiences in personalised intervention. Secondly, the research results became part of the discourse on vulnerability enabling professional security, allowing autonomous interventions for service providers. Thirdly, the service providers actively participated in the TAIS process and shaped the handbook's development and the self-reflection program's piloting period. Through this process, they gained tools to prevent professional burnout.

Viability

The TAIS beneficiaries were active participants and the creators of the development process. The different phases of the TAIS were built forward based on the results of the evaluation period. The feedback and validation from the beneficiaries were continuous. The development of the TAIS was a research-based interdependent process in which the core team adjusted the initial hypotheses to address and respond to the aspects that evolved over the piloting phase.

Capability

The beneficiaries became aware and more successful in detecting the vulnerability contexts of their clients. Through the self-reflection program, they were able to recognise, for example, how it would be worthwhile to behave differently in the helper-client relationship, to set different expectations, and to focus on the actual needs.

Inclusion

25 interviews were conducted with refugees. Menedék launched an open call for professionals to detail their work and collaboration with refugees in vulnerable situations. Intercultural mediators, psychologists, child protection professionals, social workers, legal counsellors, and volunteer helpers provided descriptions of refugees from different ethnic, religious, family, and financial backgrounds. Representatives of refugee-specific organisations took part in the ARU.

Capacity and competence

Capacity building trainings within the TAIS happened at both individual and organisational levels. Competence development of beneficiaries took place during the piloting of the self-reflection program.

Unsuccessful elements

Initially in the TAIS Menedék was also aiming to address the lack of cooperation among the different refugee-specific organisations. Due to uncertainties and safety concerns caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, this initiative did not take place. Its main purpose, i.e. fostering communication between stakeholders and service providers working with refugees in Hungary, will be reached using different methods: ARU meetings and dissemination of the training handbook.

Due to the lack of cooperation between the Hungarian mainstream and civil sector, Menedék was only able to involve the representatives of NGOs in the project. In the ARU there was one family counsellor and a member of the National Directorate-General for Aliens Policing as representatives of state institutions, however it was impossible whether TAIS results appeared in their practice.

A few NGOs were also reluctant to cooperate and Menedék has not been able to include them.

In the quintuple helix, Menedék could not find representatives from the business sector in the ARU for two main reasons: 1. No employer employs many refugees; 2. Due to the anti-refugee propaganda, business leaders were not open to collaboration.

5.6 Core results of the TAIS implementation and potential impact on beneficiaries.

In Hungary, the objective of the TAIS is to enhance refugees' embeddedness in social structures. Social workers analyse individual cases to build a "Trajectory monitoring toolbox" of helpful and tailored interventions for vulnerable refugees. It contains evidence-based "vulnerability profiles" and the description of the trajectories that these typical cases should follow in the institutional field to prevent the accumulation of vulnerabilities and reduce the isolation of vulnerable individuals. Social workers and service providers in Budapest should be informed about who, where, and how to apply helpful and tailored interventions for vulnerable refugees.

To achieve the main objective of the TAIS, by the end of the last phase two main products were created:

1. Handbook. Menedék transferred the research results of vulnerability contexts into training exercises, offering a practical task collection that processes the vulnerability of refugees living in Hungary along with current, real-life situations. In this handbook, vulnerability is described as a situation in which there is an increased risk that an individual will be harmed in some way or suffer a social or legal disadvantage that seriously affects their living conditions. It is a long-standing circumstance that limits the satisfaction of basic needs, threatens access to human rights, or even threatens identity. Another indicator of vulnerability is that the individual needs special care, support, or protection in this situation.

2. Self-reflection tool. Based on the results of mapping the vulnerability contexts, Menedék concluded that service providers are playing a pivotal role in vulnerability reduction. Menedék has noticed that there is no framework for

self-reflection neither in forms of reporting, nor in working relationships, furthermore its importance is not emphasised in the institutional level. To address the lack of self-reflection in the daily practices of service providers, Menedék built a new pilot program involving the social workers, and ARU members to develop a methodological system.

5.7 Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the ARUs' activities

In order to assure the safety of TAIS participants, some adjustments were made in the preparation. The activities and the meetings have been developed online, and the organisation has switched to remote working. So did other ARU members. These changes, however, did not have negative effects on the TAIS implementation. Furthermore, it is planned that social workers will undergo a needs/skills assessment and an online capacity building training that would help them to work with vulnerable individuals using new methods (including online communication channels). On some occasions, however, it was challenging to organise the ARU meetings and focus groups in the online space, but at the same time, it also provided new possibilities. Organising the online meetings allowed the participation of those ARU and focus group members who do not live in Budapest. A final element was planned to be added to the TAIS, namely, a multi-day workshop fostering inter-organisational cooperation among stakeholders working with refugees. Given the security concerns related to the COVID-19 pandemic, this element was not implemented. Further ARU meetings in 2022 will serve as a platform for the activities planned as part of the TAIS. Due to the confinement caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, the ARU meetings held between April 2020 and May 2021 were online. And further impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic have been reported in the section "ARUs' way of working: meetings, exchanges and decision-making process."

5.8 Sustainability of the ARUs' work after the project ends. How to keep them alive

During the project, the core research team paid attention to including ARU members connected to vulnerable refugees from various professional points of view. These different experiences of the ARU and the various roles they played in several segments of the care system were significant resources and motivators for each actor in the project. Due to the joint work, collaborations independent of the project have also developed. The level of inter-organisational trust has increased. Furthermore, in some specific cases, it has already become clear that the boundaries of responsibility and competence are better defined, which has also made the assisting work with vulnerable refugee persons more effective.

According to the opinion of the ARU members, the development process of TAIS also generated further collaborations, resulting in not only the better cooperation of the professionals but also guaranteed the multiplication of the TAIS products ensuring long-term sustainability. An ARU member pointed out that cooperation can work with daily dialogues and common discussion forums. In Hungary there is a considerable network of civil society organisations, forming for more than 20 years, that work in the field of refugee integration and advocacy. The ARU covers most of this cluster. The self-interest of these organisations is to keep ties with each other, as well as with central and local government representatives, the business sector and academia. The joint work undertaken in the ARU framework, as well as the scheduled meetings, will be a good base for future cooperation. The ARU in Hungary could develop multi-faceted response strategies for different vulnerability contexts. Trajectories of real (anonymised) people in real-life situations is now leading to the publication of a dynamic and easy-to-use guideline

that social workers can follow when they are working with forcibly displaced people with different vulnerability profiles. Using and updating this knowledge bank will be one of the key takeaways of the TAIS and of the ARU's network in Hungary.

6 The Turkish ARU - Anadolu University

6.1 Building of the ARU

Anadolu University's ARU was created in accordance with the RAISD helix methodology. Our ARU consists primarily of people from the management of Eskişehir Metropolitan Municipality, Tepebaşı Municipality, and Odunpazarı Municipality. The inclusion of municipal personnel in our ARU is of great importance since the target group of our TAIS is also Eskişehir Metropolitan Municipality social services workers. In addition, forcibly displaced people themselves took part in Anadolu University's ARU. Apart from this, local media journalists, artists, businesses and policy makers, researchers, teachers from the field of education and scientists from academic field are members of our ARU. There are also representatives from non-governmental organisations working with vulnerable groups and forcibly displaced people. From the initial creation of the ARU throughout the project, new members were added to the ARU during the implementation of our TAIS. Due to the communication efforts of the existing ARU members and the RAISD Anadolu University team, new members joined our ARU voluntarily, as the project was announced. No problems were encountered in the creation of Anadolu University ARU.

6.2 ARUs' way of working: meetings, exchanges, and decision-making process

We got together in meeting for twenty times during the project with our ARU- including the time during TAIS pilot and main trainings were being conducted. In these meetings there were ARU members from Eskişehir Metropolitan Municipality, Eskişehir Bar Association, Tepebaşı Municipality, Ülkü Primary School, Eskişehir Local Media Agencies, ESGİAD, 19 Mayıs University, Syrian and Iraqi refugee women as forcibly displaced people themselves. In each ARU meeting there were at least ten people attendance.

A shared moderation was held at Anadolu University ARU meetings. Anadolu University team did not take part as moderator in any meeting and no leadership was assumed. Within the ARU meetings, both the Anadolu University project team and the members of the ARU assumed the roles of seeking and providing information, seeking and giving ideas. A WhatsApp group was established with ARU members at the very beginning of the process before the meetings. Members were contacted regularly through this group. From time to time, meetings were held face-to-face, in small groups, in large groups, and online via Zoom with ARU members. Before each meeting, announcements of the meetings were made in WhatsApp groups.

Right at the beginning of the RAISD project, the Anadolu University team started establishing semi-formal talks and exchanges about establishing the ARU, which would hold the members of those stakeholders. Moreover, these actors (particularly centres and civil society organisations) were able to suggest other potential members and most importantly to involve FDP directly into the ARU. Simply, the Anadolu University team followed these suggestions. The main contribution was from WGSS-Women and Girls Safe Spaces centre. Through those centres, the Anadolu University team established and continued strong relations with FDP on behalf of the ARU and necessary for the ARU work. The COVID-19 outbreak and the particularly growing tension and conflicts in the country (also connected to the hate in public towards FDP), have produced an unfortunate constant change in the members of the Turkish ARU. However, their commitment in ARU and TAIS work was very effective despite the difficulties.

6.3 How were the TAIS defined by the ARU members

The Anadolu University team guided the process of TAIS definition and design, with a strong commitment and involvement in the TAIS implementation and training on behalf of the ARU members. All in all, 16 members joined the Action Research Unit, including representatives of the business and industry, policymakers, researchers, and FDP. The aim of the TAIS in Turkey is to create capacities, awareness, and understanding for various stakeholders in terms of inclusion and diversity – overall for integration – for forcibly displaced people. Through the workshops on understanding the concepts of diversity and inclusion, and the way of monitoring functions, vulnerable populations - forcibly displaced people are the main beneficiaries while society in general through various stakeholders is the beneficiary for a better integrated society.

The need for the TAIS arose fully from the beneficiary interviews of those forcibly displaced people. As being the main idea source, forcibly displaced people actively participated in the TAIS design process. All ARU members, including research, education, civil society organisations & citizens, policymakers and businesses took part in the design of the TAIS. In terms of gender equity in the team in charge of the design of the TAIS, the ratio was 60/40 in favour of female representation. All the ARU members openly and freely shared their opinions, and all agreements were made with “all agreed consensus”. In terms of inclusion and diversity in the processes, diverse aspects of gender, age, education, social status, income, ethnicity, and other aspects were all represented by ARU members.

As a result of the ARU discussions, maternal women were to be considered as the riskiest group among vulnerable groups at the current time. The fact that two thirds of Syrian refugees living in Turkey are women and girls emphasises the importance of creating solutions for women and girls among the refugee population in Turkey. Also, women are exposed to 5 types of violence including economic, sexual, psychological, physical, and emotional violence which places them in a highly vulnerable position. There are many cases and examples where women and girls are not able to access daily life practices. Therefore, women and girls among refugees may have specific problems in meeting their personal needs such as psychological support, reproductive health, etc. These can be caused by language barriers, cultural differences and accessing information mechanisms. Identifying these specific challenges and sharing them with service providers can be useful in improving the quality of services and to monitor service quality on the specific needs and challenges (especially regarding the challenges being experienced while accessing the daily life practices) of forcibly displaced women and girls.

6.4 How the ARUs started working with their TAIS, and who implemented it

Tailoring process of our TAIS was carried out effectively from the beginning of the design and planning stages. Data obtained through both FDP interviews and ARU meetings, as well as from secondary sources, indicates that forcibly displaced maternal women and girls in Turkey experience vulnerabilities in many areas of daily life, arising from different dimensions on different socio ecological levels. These vulnerabilities also lead to disruptions in accessing basic daily life practices, thus making it necessary for service providers, especially at local scale, to identify the specific conditions of these groups and develop the scope and capacity of their services. In this context, ARU interviews held within the scope of the preparation phase of the TAIS were conducted in a way that prioritises the needs of women and girls. A series of ARU meetings were held with the participation of ARU members across quintuple helix to discuss the tailoring process of TAIS. Furthermore, ensuring gender equality in participation in ARU meetings, and the gender

perspective was especially considered when defining the content of the inclusion, diversity and monitoring trainings to be provided to local service providers. In addition, to eliminate any type of miscommunication which might stem from cultural differences, a cultural mediator was present during all training sessions. Furthermore, after the training, particularly female service providers were selected to be in charge of the implementation of the monitoring process regarding the challenges of forcibly displaced women.

In our pilot trainings there were 3 trainers: 1 our project coordinator, 2 communication specialists and academicians. Prof. Dr. Erol Nezir Orhon – RAISD Anadolu University team project coordinator-, Dr. Duygu Tosunay Gencelli – expert on international communication and diplomacy communication, also an academician in the field of social sciences and communication science- and Dr. Çağlar Genç - an academician on communication sciences and expert on cultural diversity-. In TAIS main trainings there were 3 different trainers. Communication expert Pinar Alkan from United Nations, Emel Danişoğlu from social service area and Dr. Özlem Boztaş from TED University. Pinar Alkan is working in a lot of projects funded by United Nations and European Union Delegation in Turkey. She provided a lot of international policy and foreign municipality policy examples on working with vulnerable people. Emel Danişoğlu was from social service field. She was well experienced in the field of social work. She has been working with vulnerable groups in person and she is a social expert who works with public authorities. She gave a speech and examples about how to reach people on serving them to get their rights and needs. She also talked about gender equality in social works. Our last trainer was Dr. Özlem Boztaş from academic field. She is specialised on gender and has experience on local municipalities social projects as advisor and project executer. She is also an expert on rights-based and needs-based issues and monitoring. She has been involved in several projects focusing on gender equality and antidiscrimination.

There have been also new members joined in our ARU during the execution of TAIS trainings. Eskişehir Bar Association, which is expert on accessing to rights, is an example to that.

6.5 What was good and what went wrong in the TAIS

Successful Elements

For service providers, TAIS has been successful in many ways. This project's service providers consist of both Anadolu University project team and the trainers who train in TAIS pilot phase and main phase. Within the scope of the project, service providers were introduced to such concepts as "accessibility", "acceptability", "empowerment" and "viability". While focusing on rights-based and needs-based problems of the forcibly displaced people they had the opportunity to think, generate ideas and work on how the cultural adaptations they experience can be made together with both the vulnerable groups themselves and the host community. It has contributed to the inclusion of vulnerable groups in society by bringing local governments, policy makers, social workers, and forcibly displaced people together. They also had the opportunity to make suggestions to social workers working in contact with vulnerable people on how to communicate in the context of cultural diversity and vulnerability.

The beneficiaries of Anadolu University TAIS were local government service providers. This group includes social workers who work directly with vulnerable people. As well as TAIS service providers, TAIS beneficiaries were also introduced to such concepts as "accessibility", "acceptability", "empowerment" and "viability" through TAIS trainings.

The participants who stated that they did not know the concept of “vulnerable people” before the trainings, learned that people who were forcibly displaced are defined as “vulnerable”. The beneficiaries also stated that before these trainings they did not give a thought about the concepts such as diversity, cultural diversity, forcibly displaced people, vulnerability, vulnerable people, etc. They said they only had thought about these concepts superficially before and added that they had the opportunity to examine these concepts in more depth thanks to TAIS trainings. Most of the participants stated that they reconsidered their communication with the refugees they worked with after RAISD Anadolu University TAIS trainings. They stated that they mostly acted without empathy on the difficulties experienced by forcibly displaced people before. After they took these trainings, they started to think without prejudice about the difficult living conditions of forcibly displaced people. In addition, they stated that after the TAIS trainings, they were more willing and helpful in integrating forcibly displaced people into their (the host) community.

Unsuccessful Elements

In Anadolu University TAIS training, there were no unsuccessful elements that could be evaluated by the service providers. However, due to COVID-19, training processes were held online. The participants were in attendance physically. Nevertheless, trainers were from different cities, so they attended the training via zoom. And that can have a negative effect. There were no technical problems during the trainings but if the trainings could be face-to-face, it could be more interactive, there can be more activities during the trainings and beneficiaries could benefit from the training in all-purpose. Furthermore, if the trainers were attending physically, participants could act more actively on asking questions or attempting opening discussions. It may be considered not unsuccessful but a negative element of the TAIS.

In terms of the beneficiaries, for some participants; the prejudices and stereotypes they have against the forcibly displaced people during and after the training process can be considered as unsuccessful factors. Although the participants listened carefully to issues such as diversity, cultural diversity, vulnerability and forcibly displacement during the training, they consider what they learned superficially after the training. In a context of SWOT perspective, these behaviours of beneficiaries can be qualified as threats, not failures. Prior to the RAISD project, participants have never received any training on diversity, cultural diversity, vulnerability, or forcibly displaced people. It is valuable that they took this training for the first time, but they do not practice it yet. They find the subject important, but they insist on maintaining the existing attitude. Another threat that needs to be addressed in Turkey is that Turkish people themselves are vulnerable in the context of economic-political situation in our country. Therefore, we should talk about a double vulnerability while working in this country. The existing vulnerabilities of the host community cause them to look at forcibly displaced people as secondary, not internalise their problems and weaken their empathy skills towards forcibly displaced people. The participants emphasised that the economic, political and social problems in the country eroded the negative attitude towards refugees.

6.6 Core results of the TAIS implementation and potential impact on beneficiaries

In particular, during the ARU meetings, forcibly displaced people very clearly voiced their problems in accessing health, education, sheltering, employment, decision-making processes, inclusion to the host community, and other rights-based and need-based variables in daily life. The RAISD project developed a capacity for assistance that the municipality can offer indirectly, through the social services department, to the forcibly displaced people. The RAISD

project built a bridge between forcibly displaced people and municipalities in Eskişehir. Furthermore, it was an unexpected positive outcome of the RAISD project that Eskişehir Bar Association took action on vulnerability and discrimination. Eskişehir Bar Association took initiatives to establish new projects with local government stakeholders on these issues.

The goal of Anadolu University's TAIS was to develop the capacity of municipal social workers to address the vulnerabilities of forcibly displaced persons in the context of rights-based and needs-based problems. In this context, trainings were given to social workers under the headings of diversity, inclusion and monitoring. During the training, the most important outcome was that social workers did not refer forcibly displaced people as "vulnerable people". They did not think them to be forcible displaced. After the trainings and the discussions during the trainings they acknowledged who is "vulnerable" and "forcible displaced". As a result of the trainings, it is a positive outcome that all municipal personnel embrace this issue and are willing to continue the trainings. As the participants received the training, they realised their shortcomings on vulnerable groups and demanded the continuation of the trainings.

6.7 Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the ARUs' activities

COVID-19 conditions and the variability of government decisions and the uncertainty created by this situation caused difficulties in the selection of the platform where the trainings within the scope of the TAIS would be held. This situation also caused the delay of the trainings. In addition, the target audience's lack of technical proficiency in using digital platforms has hindered the delivery of all trainings remotely. In order to solve this situation, the necessity of integrating online and face-to-face platforms has emerged, and it has been deemed appropriate to implement pilot trainings in order to ensure the mentioned integration and eliminate possible problems. As a result of the pilot trainings, a mixed online and face-to-face method was applied, and the trainings were carried out in this way by taking the necessary health precautions. Meeting halls were regularly disinfected before each training and ARU meeting. Furthermore, participants were expected to provide their HES Code (a number indicating the status of the individual regarding COVID-19) and vaccination cards in order to be able to participate in the trainings. Participants who were not vaccinated or not able to show proof of vaccination at the date trainings were held, were expected to provide their PCR test results they obtained within the last 48 hours.

There have been constant changes in ARU members due to COVID-19. The new ARU members announced our project to their circles. This situation led to the joining of new members to Anadolu University's ARU. In this way, members such as artists and students joined our ARU. All ARU processes were managed through structured communication channels. While COVID-19 caused a constant change of ARU members, it also enabled many experts from different fields such as non-governmental organisations, research, business, education, and art from outside the city to participate in our ARU thanks to the online meetings. Because of COVID-19, in Turkey we had flexible working hours. In bringing our ARU members together for the meetings we had some problems from time to time. We had to reschedule or had delays. But in good cooperation with our ARU members, we had our meetings mostly in early hours of the day or after the working hours. In terms of content and efficiency we had no problems due to COVID-19. All our ARU members were very excited and committed to work with and on vulnerable and forcibly displaced people.

6.8 Sustainability of the ARUs' work after the project ends and how to keep them alive

We as RAISD Anadolu University team aim to establish a monitoring observatory together with Eskişehir Metropolitan Municipality and other official or unofficial stakeholders. The purpose of this observatory is to ensure that vulnerable or forcibly displaced people access rights-based and needs-based expectations and their inclusion to the host community. Our ARU members are expected to be natural members of this observatory.

7 The Jordanian ARU - Yarmouk University

7.1 Building of the ARU

The Jordanian ARU is led by Yarmouk University. The process of setting up the ARU started with the involvement of the Refugees, displaced persons and forced migration studies centre (RDBFMSC) at Yarmouk University and the NAWAFTH organisation for training and sustainable development in Irbid. The two institutions helped to gather and communicate with several other Jordanian stakeholders (NGOs, community leaders, associations, government organisation, academic institutions) and to reach refugees, immigrants and displaced people in Jordan. The team of the ARU is wide and distributed over Jordanian regions (North, Middle, and South) which is indeed an added value for the work of the Unit, but on the other hand it was a big challenge to find an appropriate date and time to invite them to Yarmouk University (YU), worsened by the spread of the COVID-19 in the country. The ARU is well connected with staff and members at the University, it was received positively and fit in the overall mission of the institution. The ARU is fully operational from September 2019, the first meetings with refugees were held in January 2020. Since all ARU members are highly qualified and experienced persons, their inputs have been very valuable for the project, for the definition of the vulnerability context and the design of the TAIS. Main task was indeed to get from them the highest amount of information possible.

The ARU in Jordan designed a TAIS focused on psychosocial support for refugees. The Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum (PRSF) aims to provide a structure that contributes to the well-being of individuals and prevents the need for medical support through non-clinical interventions. It aims at breaking barriers and creating connections, promoting awareness, and understanding of the importance of psychosocial support (PSS) and sharing knowledge on approaches, research, practice, and policy that impact on the provision of support to vulnerable forcibly displaced people. The TAIS in Jordan aims at implementing psychosocial support through economic empowerment and promoting financial knowledge. Health awareness, legal awareness, and psychological well-being are also key elements in the support mechanism.

7.2 ARUs' way of working: meetings, exchanges, and decision-making process

Jordanian teams worked with two different groups of ARU members in two phases: TAIS selection and TAIS design and implementation. Also, through the three phases of TAIS design and implementation, new ARU members were engaged in the work due to the need.

TAIS selection

Two workshops (focus groups) with different representatives from different I/NGOs, CBOs, NPOs, and PVOs, policy makers and academic researchers. One workshop with refugees. These workshops were held and organised by Nawafeth for training and sustainable development.

At the beginning, two workshops were held with ARU members with different experiences that support the refugees in different areas. ARU members were invited representing different I/NGOs, CBOs, NPOs, and PVOs, which provide services to refugees in Jordan. Also academic, policy makers, and refugees were invited. The essential topics that have been discussed during these 15-hours workshops were focusing on: the best practices that could be chosen to

develop an inclusion strategy in Jordan, the nature and tools that NGOs used in order to support and provide services to refugees, and how NGOs can participate in achieving the overall RAISD project goals. RAISD-YU team conducted individual meetings with NGOs' representatives to understand their operational procedures, workflows and intentions towards their support programs. One of these workshops' session was held with refugees to listen to them and including them in the TAIS creation.

TAIS design and implementation

Through TAIS design and implementation, YU-team engaged ARU members who were working in the psychological support services. These stakeholders represent the different social actors, following the principle of quintuple helix used in RRI, including:

- Highly vulnerable groups among the FDP.
- Research community (Academics) who are educational community (Universities).
- Policymakers (national government, local organisations).
- Civil society members (NGOs and citizens) that work with refugees, internally displaced people, and asylum seekers.
- ARU member from media.

A WhatsApp group was created to ease the communication among ARU members. YU-team (Dr. Amani) has the responsibility to contact them and to directly reply to their comments and notes. During the first phase (design), four face-to-face and two online meetings (workshops) were held. The date of each workshop was decided through WhatsApp.

Next phases of implementation (second and third round) meetings (workshops) were held as needed. When YU-team has specific questions for a specialist in the topic is, a personal contact with this ARU member has been done through e-mail, WhatsApp messages and calls.

As difficulties, The YU team found that most of NGOs do not share programs and refugee data with each other, so, it will be hard to share them with YU team. So, many of them refused to sign the MOU document. Many of ARU members lost their job during COVID19 and nowadays they are as freelancers.

7.3 How were the TAIS defined by the ARU members.

The design process started in August 2019, with refugee interviews. 30 interviews were held. During these interviews, RAISD-YU team asked many questions and saved notes. RAISD-YU team spent two months reading previous reports and literature to have ideas about best and bad practices in dealing with refugees in Jordan.

In early 2020, RAISD-YU team conducted several meetings and sessions with the ARU members to discuss the challenges, needs and type of services refugees face in the host country. During these sessions, RAISD-YU team explained the meaning of TAIS, the aims, the concept of RRI, and the evaluation process. They also presented their notes on the held interviews, focus group meetings with refugees, and what they got from previous studies and reports. One of the challenges and problems that was addressed during these sessions is the psychological support services that many NGOs had conducted and implemented previously. These services had many gaps: the weakness

of the training materials, recruitment of some unqualified PSS trainers, psychological support services incompetence with regards to refugees needs. Although there is a great number of refugees in desperate need for PSS, there is insufficient fund that only cover a small group of people. Therefore, RAISD-YU team and the ARU members highlighted these gaps and agreed that the TAIS needs perfectly arose from the aforementioned challenges. Also, the TAIS needs heavily relied on finding qualified experts in the PSS, building up well-developed training materials related to psychological support, working on effective assessment, and evaluation of the training materials. For sustainability purposes, it was suggested that it is important to create an online platform that would help to provide psychological support services to refugees online.

PRSF has been designed to deliver various services that contribute to minimise the effects of psychological and social challenges. These services include psychological services, social support, family services, healthcare access, economic support, and legislative support. They would contribute to improve the asylum seekers' lifestyle and enable them to integrate in the host community.

To achieve effective and efficient integration among the delivery of these services, the RPSS (Refugee Psychological Support System) program has been divided into a set of cohesive packages. The ARU members began to prepare the training material of each package under the supervision of RAISD-YU team and Dr. Ahmad Alshraifin—a specialist and a professor of psychological counselling and mental health. The ARU members were trained on how to create an effective training program which connects theory, practice, and social values. Also, Dr. Nader Rifai (a specialist in assessment and evaluation) trained the ARU members on Evaluation process and methods. The design process was coordinated and validated by RAISD-YU team and ARU members while the whole planning process was strongly coordinated by RAISD-YU team.

7.4 How the ARUs started working with their TAIS, and who implemented it

During the TAIS implementation, the PRSF were adjusted to meet specific needs at the group level and individual level as well. Comments were collected at the individual level either through the online platform or face-to-face discussions. These notes were taken periodically to develop the pilot programs to meet specific needs. At the end of each pilot, there was a revision process for the TAIS (RPSF) development methodology and training materials so the TAIS were adapted and changed.

PRSF has been designed to deliver various services that contribute to minimise the effects of psychological and social challenges. PPSRF opened the door for the participation of stakeholders working with ARU members and members of the research team along to share experiences, exchange data, and build up training programs to support the target group. Five different topics were implemented by the PRSF through supporting: economic empowerment and promoting financial knowledge, social support and refugee status, health and legal awareness, and empowerment and psychological well-being.

After the first TAIS round, new collaborators were needed in order to play a great part in the efficiency and success of the TAIS. The first step was presenting to collaborators the needs refugees must have to enhance inclusion in the host community which is psychological support in five areas (legal, health, economic, psychological support, and family empowerment). For the II and III TAIS round, an evaluation and assessment collaborator was needed to measure and analyse the validity of the training programs. We also turned to the expertise of 58 specialists, university

professors and experts, specialised in preparing training programs about the mentioned fields. Their feedback was helpful in adjusting some activities and practices within the training design to assure the efficiency of the training programs. Trainers who were part of the national and international ARU were needed to implement the training programs. Each specialist trainer engaged with the related topic and understood what the TAIS was trying to achieve in order to ascertain the success and efficiency of the training material. This was measured by observing the participants' willingness to continue with the training and the communication between the trainers and the participants.

7.5 What was good and what went wrong in the TAIS

Successful elements

The YU-team believes that there are many successful elements in the TAIS program, and the evidence is available from the perspective of both beneficiaries and service providers. The following paragraphs will demonstrate these elements following RAISD's evaluation criteria (process and outcome):

Passing on knowledge: One of the main advantages for participants was increasing their knowledge and experiences when undergoing the different training workshops. This included equipping participants with a wide range of information and skills besides correcting many misunderstood concepts according to participants and service providers.

Quality training: participants highlighted three main reasons why they enjoyed the training and these are:

- First: the trainer, who was organised, facilitated concepts, and explained things smoothly, who was passionate, had a sound knowledge of the subjects and a distinguished teaching style.
- Second, the training material and content: which was excellent, rich, comprehensive, unique, and different from similar training courses, rich topics, beneficial information, suitable for people needs, relevant to what we need today in these circumstances.
- Third, the interaction with attendees through asking questions and answering them, the summaries are given by the trainer, and the pace of the training was convenient.

Accessibility: participants had no problems in reaching the TAIS training. It was easy for them to reach the training regardless of gender, background, or ability. Furthermore, beneficiaries were diverse in terms of gender, age, and education.

Acceptability: beneficiaries have a high level of acceptance for the program since the statistics show a full attendance record for all the beneficiaries during the full program. Results show that the topics discussed during the training meet the needs, interests, and abilities of different beneficiaries. The deep discussions that took place between beneficiaries and the trainer are strong evidence of the beneficiary's acceptance of the TAIS training.

Empowerment: It was evident that the TAIS training program succeeded in increasing the beneficiaries' level of knowledge and in equipping them with the necessary concepts which will facilitate their integration into the host societies. This should help them too in creating opportunities and in achieving their different duties as many of them are parents, students, or employees. Further, it should help them to identify important areas that are vital to their

professional, psychological or health developments. Getting certificates at the end of the training should contribute to their self-development and create some work opportunities with some local or international agencies working with refugees.

Viability: Beneficiaries stated that TAIS training is important to them and that it will have an impact on their self-development. They were keen to attend all the sessions and they kept a full level of attendance during the program. Both, the service providers and the beneficiaries agree that the TAIS training matches with the local institutional and professional culture and that it can grow and expand.

Capability: According to beneficiaries, the TAIS training had an impact on their autonomy and helped them to fit in the society and become fully integrated and productive members of the society. Therefore, such training might be a driving factor towards real change in the refugee's level of coping in the context of host communities.

Inclusion: Due to the allowed time for evaluation, there was little chance to identify evidence on contributing the training towards inclusion and integration of beneficiaries in the host communities. However, the TAIS training promotes beneficiaries to start active societal participation through developing their social networks and working on community engagement with the surroundings. Many of the beneficiaries are keen to join local universities and do their degrees, postgraduate, or professional training courses.

Capacity: Beneficiaries managed to keep the learning from the TAIS training for one month later. This highlights the extent to which the TAIS training influences skills of the beneficiaries. Acquiring the necessary concepts and the main skills in the field of training will help the beneficiaries further to know more about work and educational opportunities and on the right and available services.

Unsuccessful elements, areas for improvement

- Beneficiaries want to learn more about issues related to the training materials, this might be understood in different ways: this desire implies their enjoyment of the experience of learning they are going through. It indicates a training need that has not been met yet or a challenge that they are facing in society and need to be dealt with.
- In one or two sessions, there was a need to invest more in the time allocated for training. This problem impacted the delivery of some parts of the program.
- On one occasion, it was hard to keep distance among participants due to the limited free spaces in the training room; yet, the training venue and environment was another limitation.
- The colours used in the PowerPoint presentation were blurry and the text was messy.

To further enhance the good level of interaction and engagement during some training sessions, participants suggested three areas for development:

- A. creating more space for asking questions and discussions.
- B. encouraging active participation and overcoming the barriers of fear and shame among participants.
- C. maintaining the ice-breaking activities at the beginning of each training workshop.

Training environment: the limited amenities of the training venue (only one workshop) have impacted the training quality. Since the training room was small, there was no chance to carry out any group-based learning activities. Therefore, the training style remained traditional and centred on the lecturer all the time.

Training administration: there was no evidence on some important (only one workshop) issues such as: a) briefing participants about the program of the day; b) no blueprint of the training program; c) no 'code of conduct' to organise the relationship among different parties in the workshop (i.e. organising the overuse of mobile, leaving the training room, and taking notes during the training); d) no seating plan in the training room; e) no ice-breaking activities during the training program.

Competence: There was no evidence of the possible influence of TAIS over the competencies and skills of the service providers.

7.6 Core results of the TAIS implementation and potential impact on beneficiaries

Through analysing the evaluation of the TAIS, we expect that the TAIS have a positive impact on the lives of the beneficiaries, FDP and ARU members. For FDP, TAIS addresses psychological support in five main fields. One of its main objectives is to enable FDP to become instruments / agents of transformative change in their own lives, households, and in the life of their communities. One of the unexpected positive impacts was within the legal empowerment field in which many FDP were not aware of their legal rights in the host community. We have also realised that there is a huge change within the mind-set of FDP after spending almost 10 years in Jordan. At the beginning, refugees were focussing on survival and attaining their basic needs. What we have noticed during the implementation process, through the question-answer response, was that refugees are willing to improve their conditions via education, entrepreneurship, and self-psychological treatment. They utilise what they learn from training programs to improve their livelihoods. As for ARU members, the TAIS methodology was an effective methodology that infused the stakeholders to follow in order to develop their training designs.

7.7 Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the ARUs' activities

Due to COVID-19 Yarmouk campus has been closed, so YU team looked for place to conduct the meetings. Online meetings and personal contact were being held to go over the COVID-19 lockdown. As a result of the outbreak of COVID-19, governments issued orders to close schools, universities, centres and most sectors as a precautionary measure to prevent the spread of infection. Jordan was the first country in the region to respond to the crisis, by imposing a curfew, and closing all educational institutions across the Kingdom; these measures made it one of the countries that succeeded in relatively controlling the numbers of injuries and deaths in that period.

Here, it can be noted that during the pandemic, the refugees experienced many psychological stimuli accompanying anxiety, stress, depression, and many psychological effects that need immediate psychological support. Considering the emerging COVID-19 crisis, refugees have faced a set of changes without preparation. In advance, such as having to isolate from the outside world due to the imposition of domestic isolation, which led to the loss of their temporary work that used to meet their personal and material needs. It may have many severe psychological effects related to their mental and physical health.

As a result of the repeated closures in that period and the prevention of gatherings, meetings were held via the Zoom program, in addition to holding meetings of no more than 20 people, and this led to an increase in the burden and preparations. Data collection from refugees was done through an electronic link designed, and sent via WhatsApp, phone call and their e-mail, and participants were free to answer or not. There were difficulties and restrictions in holding workshops, especially with the allowed number, size of the room where the workshop was held and the ability of the refugee to attend due to the lack of public transportation.

7.8 Sustainability of the ARUs' work after the project ends and how to keep them alive

YU-team will do:

- Prepare documents about RAISD methodology in Arabic language and simple written.
- Documentation about evaluation methods and how, when and where can be used.
- Publish these documents (documentary).

YU-team already trained the ARU members in different RAISD methodology and evaluation topics such as RRI, Action research, evaluation, etc.

8 Lebanese ARU at the Lebanese International University

8.1 Building of the ARU

Starting from the Guidebook developed by UNIMED at the beginning of the RAISD project, the Lebanese International University, in charge of the Lebanese ARU, started working on the establishment of the research unit and on selecting the members and stakeholders to be involved in the process. At the very beginning, LIU started with the idea of involving the Centre of Excellence for research and Development which was very instrumental to ARU. The Centre vision was to lead research and work on developing a research culture at the university, fostering an environment conducive to research and the creation of knowledge. The rationale is to undertake research which both enhances the learning experience of students, and delivers influence on economy, society, culture, public policy or services, health, environment, and quality of life, beyond contributions to academia. In this sense, the work of the Centre was in line with the objective and scope of the RAISD research units.

Moreover, with LIU dispersed in 9 geographic areas in Lebanon, the university had the potential to involve a high number of stakeholders from different regions and disciplines, from the project focal point to the university governance (represented by the Provost and the Vice-President who joined several meetings), researchers and colleagues from the Excellence Centre. For the ARU to be established, it was rather easy to draft a list of possible ARU members with strong relationships with the civil society and with their territory. It was a founding principle that different professional skills should be represented, involving figures with expertise in social work, child protection, training and education, legal help and policy analysis, and also key stakeholders who work directly with refugees. In Lebanon and due to the chaos faced by the country, LIU found difficulties to have representatives of the business helix, which would have improved the impact on the project.

Yet, one of the big issues that LIU faced was the first political unrest that hit the country from October 2019 till mid-December of 2019. As of January 2020, participants were so cautious with discussing and providing data. Second, traveling around the country was impeded with roadblocks by the so-called revolutionists. Later, with the COVID-19 outbreak, it was almost impossible to hold meetings in presence, and even the focus of the ARU drastically changed. While still working on refugees' inclusion, LIU focused the work of the ARU (and the TAIS) on health literacy and support to the refugees in the camp to cope with the virus.

In terms of numbers, 4 LIU permanent staff members were involved in the preparation, coordination, and follow-up of the ARU meetings, as well as the facilitation of the meetings. After the pandemic outbreak, and the necessity to adapt to the changed environment, in April 2021 the LIU Health Committee was created to follow up on the significant developments of the COVID-19 and to design precautions to vulnerable people as recommended. The staff dedicated to the ARU work proved to have expertise with both refugee inclusion, as well as good knowledge of both English and Arabic. With the COVID-19 outbreak, and to cope with the difficulties generated by the pandemic, a staff member from the LIU Health Committee was also involved to work in tandem with the objectives of the ARU. As a result, policymakers, researchers, experts, and strategic institutional figures were engaged in the ARU, building on the principles of excellence and inclusion. More stakeholders were in the plan, but due to a number of unforeseen risk factors, their direct involvement was not possible; instead, they were consulted as interviewees for the definition of the vulnerability context and the TAIS.

8.2 ARUs' way of working: meetings, exchanges, and decision-making process

After the establishment of the ARU, LIU staff members worked carefully to clarify to stakeholders the objective of their involvement, meaning the contribution in the definition of the vulnerable context and the TAIS, gathering information and processing this information with an RRI approach, thus contributing to the TAIS piloting and evaluation.

The ARU was officially operational from December 2019, while the first ARU meeting was held in January 2020, followed by meetings in February. Later, with the COVID-19 outbreak, it was almost impossible to hold face-to-face meetings, since the university was closed and stakeholders were prevented from joining. However, consultations continued virtually, and LIU staff members, together with the Health Committee, kept the work of the ARU up and running. Therefore, while the preliminary ARU meetings were organised and held face to face, with the outbreak of COVID all subsequent meetings were done virtually and using other social media. Invariably, the discussions revolved around ways and means to address the devastating risks refugees and vulnerable groups among forcibly displaced were exposed to amidst the COVID-19 pandemic and economic crisis as many were already victims of post-traumatic stress disorder.

To overcome difficulties in the decision-making process, ARU members co-created a Journey Map to follow up on recommendations and other suggestions made to enhance research and development of the project. As for ARU members that were not directly involved in the TAIS, to cope with the risk of alienating or losing their participation in the project, several informational and educational meetings were held. All ARU members immensely contributed, had clear ideas on how to contribute, how to play a role in the crisis and shared recommendations. Among them, a member (a former government minister) distinctly stood out. His influential presence, motivational tone and message inspired stakeholders' attendees to voice their concerns, share ideas at such meetings.

The COVID-19 pandemic had both financial and activity-related effects on a number of areas of activity. Lebanon was badly hit, while still recovering from the riots of late 2019. The Beirut port blast was another major unforeseen factor that also exacerbated the pressing situation in the country in general and LIU in particular. All activities were put on hold for weeks as the situation of political hostility erupted in the aftermath of the explosion (August, 2021). Consequently, all ARU activities failed to reach their full capacity, after halting all initially targeted activities that were supposed to be done in physical spaces. The research underlying RAISD, and the TAIS, had to adapt to new challenges and re-order priorities.

With regards to the process of work, we consider the TAIS program to be successful in terms of promoting accessibility and empowerment. The outcome was considered to be efficacious in connection with the beneficiary's capacities and range of competencies, aiding them in becoming more conscious of their own strengths and capabilities. With regards to the success factors, we would consider it to be reflected in the implementation of application in their university work.

The ARU collaboration during the entire process has been of immense value, especially with regards to detecting VGs, designing the TAIS and working during the sessions. Our ARU was definitely one of the success factors of the LIU TAIS in the area of Bekaa close to Syria.

8.3 How were the TAIS defined by the ARU members

TAIS arose from interviews done with forcibly displaced people and secondary sources. ARU members and advisory board members played an important role in creating the TAIS outline. The details of TAIS were also discussed in several meetings which included ARU members with forcibly displaced people (vulnerable groups), all project researchers and voluntary academicians. Due to COVID-19, such online meetings addressed the alarming health problems and massive withdrawal from camps of displaced refugees and the underprivileged affected by the pandemic. The elderly, maternal women and young infants are the riskiest groups among vulnerable groups. Accessing basic health services is one of the most challenging issues for such vulnerable groups. Many refugees in Lebanon lack access to free healthcare services, as they do not have legal refugee status. In tandem, the problem of accessing information mechanisms is also prevalent, the more so due to cost COVID-19 testing and lack of hospital beds to accommodate those stricken by the virus.

According to ARU and AB members, access to information and education about COVID and how to confront it was a major challenge. Therefore, the LIU Health Committee was created and focused on awareness raising among refugee populations. The Lebanese TAIS was restructured to provide a series of training and instruction about health awareness, health protection and health response to fit vulnerable people's needs. Since the outbreak of the pandemic, there had been dire predictions and fear about the fact that crowded refugee camps in Lebanon would become fertile grounds for the virus because of the inability of people to socially distance, inadequate water supply, sanitation and hygiene facilities and inadequate access to health care and inadequate community awareness. The pandemic's indirect effects have had the biggest impact on the vulnerabilities of refugees and forcibly displaced people in various ways who also are highly influenced by legal status: rising economic hardships as informal work opportunities have decreased, threats of eviction due not paying rent, inability to buy sanitary items to protect themselves from the virus and subjected to stigmatising and discrimination. Such increased domestic tensions and abuse due to prolonged periods of lockdown confinement, resort to harmful coping mechanisms such as women and girls facing increased exposure to gender-based violence and worsening gender inequality, taking children out of school and putting them to work, further reducing access to education, healthcare and rising mental distress.

The team members were mostly university instructors and researcher profiles at LIU. The contents addressed were:

- December 4, 2020: share the concept of developing videos and brochures for Health Guidelines. Review of tasks 2) Update from MOPH 3) Posters 4) Episodes 5) Research Ideas 6) Ramadan Ideas 7) RAISD ERASMUS + project 8) New Ideas.
- January 15, 2021: messages shared on Google Classroom for all 35 vulnerable individuals posting four surveys for a virtual meeting on that day.
- January 21, 2021: invitation to join the webinar "COVID-19 Vaccine: Between Theory and the Practice". This was a part of our awareness campaign to all vulnerable people in camps based on ARU recommendation.
- February 1, 2021: IT Literacy development strategy to 35 vulnerable individuals. All recorded on google site.

The context of health risks produced by COVID-19 was especially emphasised by the group of beneficiaries, which validated the design of the TAIS and expressed their needs and expectations. From the very beginning, the design of

the training had to be adapted to the online modality and for this a new detection of resources was necessary to set the training Module between December 2020 and January 2021.

8.4 How the ARUs started working with their TAIS, and who implemented it

As mentioned in the precedent paragraph, the history of the Lebanese ARU and the work on the TAIS has varied frequently over time, under the pressure of continuous adaptations. After the final re-direction of the TAIS towards Health awareness for refugees in the camps, to cope with the COVID-19 pandemic, a first round of training was conducted. As a consequence of the first evaluation, immediate action to form a Health Committee was developed.

Table 6: Profile of TAIS implementers. Lebanon

Profile of TAIS implementers					
Total number:	10	Female:	4	Male:	6
Number of research staff:	6	Female:	1	Male:	5
Number of administrative:	4	Female:	1	Male:	3
Number of training experts:	10	Female:	4	Male:	6
Number of technical staff:	1	Female:	0	Male:	1

8.5 What was good and what went wrong in the TAIS

Successful elements

Apart from continuously gathering information from the organising team and doing participatory observations, the LIU team carried out an outcome evaluation through in-depth meetings by the Health Committee headed by Dr. Ahmad Faraj with 2 vulnerable students. The students provided valuable insights and recommendations for future initiatives.

According to the outcomes of the evaluation, and the experience of the members and stakeholders working on the TAIS was very positive. The head of the HEALTH committee noted that all the students have experienced an improvement in their professional, interpersonal skills and capacities as a result of the TAIS. Not only did they improve with regards to their capacity to open up, but also became more confident with regards to the job application process and interacting with university life at LIU. In addition, two of them even volunteered to take part in the production of the ARU stories shared with UNIMED. This augmented self-confidence was reflected in their more fluid and active participation with their core assistance NGOs, such as Tatweer Baladna.

Refugees empowered with new health awareness and skills passed their competences to others. Beneficiaries stated that the training was enriching, beneficial, and raised awareness. One of the interviewees reflected that she used all the information acquired with her students. The other pointed out the impact this training left on him, as well as the benefits of disseminating awareness and knowledge in camps, especially the Bekaa area, most highly condensed.

When it comes to process criteria, the Lebanese ARU members think that the TAIS program was successful in terms of accessibility and empowerment. The outcome was successful in terms of improving the beneficiary's capacities and their package of competences, helping them to become more aware of their own rights and their capability to manage health risks and their consequences. There was evidence of active participation of behalf of ARU members along all phases of the project. This was obtained from the ARU meeting agendas as well as the list of participants, the log of the Health Committee meetings, and social media posts of TAIS: Evidence of the advantages of the TAIS in the LIU newsletter.

Unsuccessful elements

Even if the positive elements of the training and mentoring program were many, one of the interviewees argued that the political chaos in Lebanon sometimes acted as a demotivational element, increasing the risk of unsuccess as it contributed to a negative predisposition of some participants. Moreover, one of the service providers found that the program was launched in January 2021 after writing the adapted modules solely in December 2020, while the team would have needed to have a deeper look into the beneficiaries needs and expectations once they had been called to participate in the training.

In terms of outcome criteria, the pandemic partially hindered our ability to assist the participants in their social inclusion process, it became a harder goal to reach due to the activities online, lack of face-to-face action, missing visits to organisations and other foreseen socialisation activities.

8.6 Core results of the TAIS implementation and potential impact on beneficiaries

In Lebanon, the designed TAIS is geared at addressing social, emotional, and academic problems. The program had a positive impact on the Syrian people in camps in addition to delivering a holistic Corona Virus awareness to children, pregnant women, elderly people, malnourished people, and people who are ill or immune-compromised. RAISD team in Lebanon, through its Health committee worked to enrich all stakeholders with the coping tools needed to raise their awareness and minimise challenges and trauma they were and continue to face amidst and beyond the COVID 19 pandemic and the dire economic situation and plethora of crises in Lebanon which has had also difficult hardships visited upon Syrian refugees and vulnerable people.

The aim of the TAIS was to deliver an online awareness campaign, called Health 4 SEAD "Health, Social Emotional, Academic, Development". H 4 SEAD geared to engage in COVID-19 awareness, prevention and treatment information campaigns through online dissemination, but not limited to, community groups and religious leaders, telephone hotlines, flyers, posters, bulk SMS and WhatsApp messaging, radio announcements, focus group discussions, leaflets, billboards and mural drawings, broadcasted videos, and brochures with instructions.

The outcome of this pilot project aimed at empowering a strong pool of NGOs and Information Focal Point networks all over Lebanon in preparing them to facilitate and support their teaching efforts of Syrian, Palestinian and displaced people in refugee camps. This was done through LIU health Committee's active participation and sharing of practical experiences utilising online means. Essentially, the program centres around a plethora of different skills and capacities (digital, emotional, communication, leadership, management, and English Language) that were chosen to be a constituent of the program. The aforementioned were then validated and highlighted by various ARU members

and prospective beneficiaries in the consultation process. The skills were notable for being considered a high value benefit for university and place work of the vulnerable students as well as becoming coaches.

As previously stated, the students' competence level in leadership, digital media and communication through the medium of the English language have been contemplated. It has been noted that the students have improved with the new tools. Moreover, the TAIS has also provided them with the means to improve and develop their social support network in and outside the university, meeting for the most part the very high expectation expressed during the course of the training program.

During the course of the training, students were able to advance their capacity for reflection and constructive criticism with regards to the activity at hand, in the communication with others. The extent to which the students are actively involved in new technologies has significantly improved. This in turn has resulted in an enhancement of their communication skills as attitude with peers at university and community as they constantly relay.

The primary objective with regards to the TAIS is centred around improving their ability to empower students in the working place, to enrich their employment status or dissemination to develop awareness in Syrian camps and schools. The training also encompassed content related to gender aspects as well as human and labour rights. Likewise, details on current social and health issues, such as complex and changing movement restriction in Bekaa, have also been disseminated.

Improving their knowledge of attitude in order to acquire the means to cooperate with various teams in a more proactive manner was one the central aims of TAIS. The students were abetted in order to demonstrate such competences in the communities.

As an unexpected positive impact, we could consider that some of them became coaches in their camps. This has an important impact on their lives related to work. In terms of unexpected negative impacts, there was none of consideration. Still, the lack of personal contact with the beneficiaries might have caused some anxiety both in the trainers and trainees. Human and face-to-face contact produces effective outcomes with stronger impact.

8.7 Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the ARUs' activities

As reported before, the COVID-19 had a wide impact on the Lebanese ARU, not only in terms of the feasibility of meetings and actions (which were moved online for the most part) but also on the content of the TAIS. It is very difficult to disentangle COVID-19 from the work of the ARU and the implementation of the TAIS. Due to the pandemic outbreak, the discourse around inclusion and empowerment of refugees in Lebanon revolved around ways and means to address the devastating risks refugees and vulnerable groups among forcibly displaced were exposed to amidst the COVID-19 pandemic and the interrelated economic crisis. According to ARU and AB members, access to information and education about COVID and how to confront it was a major challenge.

As Lebanon was already going through extraordinarily difficult political, social, and economic crises, which were exacerbated further by the catastrophic Beirut Port explosion, the COVID-19 constituted an unforeseen risk factor that impacted the direction of the TAIS and the adjustments that were made to move the research process forward. Among the consequences of the pandemic, a series of lockdowns and curfews were put in place to control the spread of the virus. Therefore, in accordance with the coordinating partner of the RAISD project and the leaders of the WPs,

it was decided to move from face-to-face interviews to remote surveys and to partner with NGOs or institutions that could assist in the process, and that have previously worked with refugees and VGs in the respective study areas. Then, an online committee regarding teaching was formed and a site for online teaching was established. The support of external personnel was necessary to implement the online modality, both at the coordination level of the ARU and the Health Committee, as well as in delivering the training. The support of Health Committee was necessary to implement the online modality, to make sure the amendment of TAIS had to be made as a consequence of both the micro- level and macro- level disputes. It should be noted that the pandemic resulted in serious consequences at a health and social level as well as politically and overall security of Lebanon.

Moreover, to overcome the economic hardship resulting from the lockdown and few or non-existent work opportunities, Syrian refugees and forcibly displaced people have increased their debts, reduced the quantity and quality of food consumption and in the case of those living outside camps changed their housing due to inability to pay rent or faced evictions. In such circumstances, the impact of the COVID on the implementation of the ARU activities and way of working posed many challenges and problems. The very widespread application of lockdown measures and social distancing meant that all activities judged to be non-essential were almost completely stopped, including most of the activities related to the ARU functioning. Consequently, all ARU activities risked failing to reach their full potential.

8.8 Sustainability of the ARUs' work after the project ends. How to keep them alive

In order to answer the question “How will the ARUs continue to work after the end of the project?” ARU members were asked to think ‘outside the box’ to develop innovative solutions to the complex problems faced. The Lebanese colleagues stated the need to work outside the conventional iron triangle of project management and employ a long-term impact approach. The relation between future preparedness for sustainability of ARUs and how it may benefit or impact future research on refugee and vulnerable populations is a two-way street. On one hand, projects shape the future as in the case of ARUs on vulnerability, whilst on the other hand, how the next three years shall unfold is critical to ARUs given the likelihood of political and cultural uncertainties and their effects.

One of the elements to grant sustainability of the ARU, and to enforce the future perspective of the research unit, is to nurture a broad base of community support, building and maintaining diverse supportive stakeholder’s groups through:

- Continue to involve local leaders from business, government, faith-based organisations, non-profit NGOs, and others throughout the TAIS implementation and the activities of the ARU.
- Form partnerships with organisations that serve the same population, be clear on new roles and responsibilities, and establish or revise memoranda of understanding, if appropriate.
- Build positive relationships with local media.
- Start imagining future joint actions.
- Include the youth and families we served during the project.
- Develop the leadership skills of key stakeholders (ARU) so they can educate others about the project and the inclusion strategies put in place.

9 Conclusions

It is not easy to draw general conclusions from this collection of inputs from 7 ARUs so deeply different from all viewpoints, including the geopolitical context, language, culture, political situation, and contents of the TAIS. However, in this final section we have tried to identify some issues which, although they may not refer to all the ARUs, at least were raised in a number of them. In doing so, we have used the same structure as in the individual sections related to each individual ARU.

Building the ARUs

While building the Research Units partners followed a number of guidelines which mainly focused on including a wide range of different actors and stakeholders representing the quintuple helix. In order to do so, and to rely on a strong expertise for the definition of the TAIS and the vulnerable context, partners leveraged on their previous experiences in research projects and initiatives with vulnerable groups. Welcoming actors and experts from different fields ensured a solid base to the ARU, followed by an ongoing process of engagement of stakeholders.

ARUs applied a double side approach (top-down and bottom-up) to allow all voices to be heard and contributing to strengthening the dialogue among members themselves.

Difficulties were found by some of the ARUs in reaching all five blades of the Quintuple Helix, especially the private sector and government bodies. In fact, those ARUs which managed to involve a wide range of stakeholders representing all the five blades of the Quintuple Helix felt stronger in their action.

Variable composition of the ARU was also a problem, especially because in many cases the members of the same ARU changed over time, thus reducing the common knowledge about the TAIS and the mutual knowledge among the ARU members. On the other side, the inclusion of new members upon necessity has been a positive unexpected outcome.

Language problems were also a major component in communicating with FDP (EU-based ARUs) and internally (local language vs English). Language has been a key tassel in TAIS implementation with language skills being among the basic skills to be passed to FDP. Still, it stayed as a challenge for the functioning of the ARUs themselves.

ARUs' way of working: meetings, exchanges, and decision-making process

All ARUs worked performing many meetings, at first in presence, later virtually due to the pandemic outbreak. During the meetings ARU members worked together for the definition of the vulnerable context in which they were going to operate, and to co-design the TAIS. All ARUs reported that different actors were actively involved making all voices heard. Decision-making was shared among the core ARU members, and decisions were reported to everyone. Adaptations were needed and all ARUs reported the great capacity of the working groups to adapt in the most effective ways.

In terms of challenges, many ARUs identified problems related to the language of beneficiaries (many of them are not familiar with the local language) and to the protection of their identity, so as to create trust: it is common experience that many migrants and especially refugees are reluctant to be identified as such. Also, in some of the RAISD countries, the government is not keen in supporting migrants and this makes things more complicated.

As a recommendation, much transparency and communication efforts are required.

How were the TAIS defined by the ARU members

Co-design and participatory approach were the key elements in the definition of TAIS which would be useful for the target FDP. Interviews and consultations were put in place with potential beneficiaries, vulnerable people, research experts and stakeholders.

This process often greatly increased the ARU members' (and especially the project partners') knowledge of the problems and histories of the FDP groups they decided to address. A thorough research process and wide-ranging consultations for the definition of the VC, vulnerable groups, and finally the TAIS, were essential, along with the acknowledgement of the importance of a tailored approach.

Moreover, brainstorming of ideas allowed to explore the full potential of the actions.

How the ARUs started working with their TAIS, and who implemented it

Once again, the participatory approach was key to deepen and adapt the implementation of the TAIS to the real needs of the selected target groups. Among the main activities put in place: continuous meetings, action-oriented assessments, involvement of new experts all along the process and to respond to the changing environment and priorities.

Language problems (especially in EU countries) and access to IT equipment and software had to be solved. In fact, the digital divide and the availability of computers and other devices raised as a problem, amplified by the fact that due to the outbreak of the COVID-19, many activities had to be converted from physical to online.

In many cases it was necessary to recruit external experts, such as IT Companies, social workers, or academic lecturers to cope with specific needs related to the implementation of the TAIS, specifically due to the shift to the online mode, which caught many unprepared and/or unqualified and unskilled.

The need for training the trainers has been identified by many ARUs, not in terms of enhancing their knowledge of the topics, but rather on the way of communicating with FDP who have a different cultural background and sometimes a difficulty of understanding the local language.

Many adaptations were needed due to the pandemic and ARU showed a great capacity in re-designing initiatives and adapting to the changing environment as well as to the results of the piloting and assessment process. Such a dynamic approach and a constant flow of communications with the beneficiaries and among the members were also points of strength in the implementation of the TAIS by the ARUs.

What was good and what went wrong in the TAIS

Successful Elements

1. Improvement of capacities and strengthening of both professional and personal skills. This in turn increased the self-confidence and autonomy of beneficiaries.
2. Inclusion and support provided to participants, but also networking among them, increased social interactions, a support network and empowered FDP.
3. Increased professional contacts and job opportunities in the local context.
4. Cross fertilisation among different operational actors of the TAIS implementation, as well as the interactions with the beneficiaries, strongly increased the understanding about the real problems of the FDP on behalf of these actors.
5. Personal growth of the beneficiaries, although this was not always enough to fully meet their expectations.

Generally speaking, it is possible to say that the most successful TAISs were those which implemented training and capacity building rather than those which attempted to implement new services. This is probably due to the sustainability of the action: new knowledge, once acquired, remains with the beneficiary, whereas new services which need financial support and resources have to stop when these disappear.

Unsuccessful Elements

1. Reduction in beneficiaries' number in some cases and reduced engagement of many. This was mainly due to the shift to online meetings and online training, for which operators were not fully prepared and participants felt less involved and supported.
2. Digital unpreparedness.
3. Difficulties in welcoming vulnerable participants in the correct facilities, and other problems related to the logistics of the TAIS during the pandemic.
4. The training path did not always fully meet the beneficiaries' expectations, due to (at least) two different factors: the final goals were not communicated clearly enough, and the expectations were too high (such as finding a job at the end of the path).
5. Difficulties were reported from some of the ARUs in the process of recruiting both on the side of service providers and of final beneficiaries, and of keeping them involved until the end of the pilots.
6. In many countries the national policies concerning migrants, asylum seekers and refugees changed over time, thus creating difficulties in implementing the TAIS.

Core results of the TAIS implementation and potential impact on beneficiaries

This section is extremely heterogeneous as the level of achievement of results is very uneven across the seven ARUs. However, generally speaking, most of the partners felt satisfied with the outcome of their actions and beneficiaries reported great benefits due to the involvement in the project and in the initiatives put in place by the ARUs.

The Spanish ARU returned a rather positive evaluation of the achievement of results, in terms of entrepreneurship skills development, with a significant number of the final beneficiaries having found a job or started their own activity. A social support network for the TAIS beneficiaries was developed and improved, reducing the feeling of loneliness

along with increasing their autonomy and soft skills to complement the technical skills on which were trained. As a result, their employability in the local market resulted definitely higher.

The Italian ARU declared to be satisfied with the results of the implementation of the TAIS, both in terms of technical results (the learning platform) and of the impact on the beneficiaries. A new methodology for learning was developed and resulted to be successful. Training materials for both vulnerable women and girls, and for trainers and educators, were developed. Beneficiaries increased their language skills, their knowledge of the local context providing rights and opportunities, and finally they felt authors of their own paths. The link to the territory and breaking down cultural and language barriers increased their feeling of confidence and protection.

The Finnish ARU reported a partial level of achievement of tangible results, primarily because the impacts of measures in the social field are less tangible and may become visible only in the medium/long term. Beneficiaries reported an increased knowledge of the Finnish language, culture, and institutions with the potential of improving their living conditions. One of the main setbacks were the limited number of participants which finally participated to both TAIS and the difficulties in using the facilities of the centres.

The Hungarian ARU declared to have produced the expected results (a Handbook and a Self-reflection tool) and appears to be satisfied with the outcome of the initiative. Being addressed to social workers in daily contact with refugees, these tools and mostly the self-reflection program provided them with a new awareness in detecting the vulnerability contexts and in recognising when behaving differently in the helper-client relationship, to set different expectations, and to focus on the actual needs.

The Turkish ARU also declared to be satisfied with the results obtained, especially in terms of increased awareness by the social workers involved in the TAIS about the real problems and vulnerabilities of the FDP they work with. During ARU meetings FDP clearly voiced their problems in accessing health, education, sheltering, employment, decision-making processes, inclusion to the host community, and other rights-based and need-based variables in daily life. Therefore it was possible to build a bridge between them and the ARU members as well as with the local communities and actors.

The Jordanian ARU is also satisfied with the results of their TAIS especially in terms of enhanced knowledge of the FDP problems but also in terms of positive impact on their lives. Beneficiaries were empowered to be fully aware of their legal rights in host communities. They also reported a huge change in the mind-set, which combined with new skills and professional capacities increased their livelihood.

In spite of all the dreadful events which hit Lebanon in the last couple of years, the local ARU declared to be reasonably satisfied with the achieved results, especially in terms of the training outcomes for the refugees and other beneficiaries but also in terms of the potential of the cascade effect, raising awareness well beyond the direct targets of the TAIS.

Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the ARUs' activities

COVID-19 had a huge and mostly negative impact for all the ARUs, having forced them to turn physical activities into online ones whenever possible, and reducing the capacity of the TAIS to produce the set benefits. This created several difficulties:

- Access to IT equipment (tablets and PCs).
- Digital divide: many beneficiaries, but also many trainers, were not used to interacting with technology for work and training.
- Reduction of face-to-face interactions, which facilitate communication and socialisation. This in turn generated a feeling of isolation on behalf of the already vulnerable and fragile groups.
- Reduced effectiveness of the trainings, where delivered.
- Language difficulties increased by the online modality of interaction.

If a positive effect can be tracked out of the pandemic, was to have increased the digital skills of all actors involved, beneficiaries, ARU members, trainers, etc. The forced shift to the online dimension allowed for the development of innovative and creative solutions and resources, and pushed many to learn about new technologies and approaches.

Sustainability of the ARUs' work after the project ends and how to keep them alive

One of the main sustainability elements for the project is the setting up of the RAISD Observatory on Forced Migration, an international collaborative organism created among project partners and that has already started its activity in March 2021 and that will continue working after the project finishes, with local branches and activities in project countries and driven by the coordinating partner.

Furthermore, several recommendations were formulated by the Advisory Board members on the occasion of a Consortium meeting held on the 4th of November 2021, they are reported in the section related to the Spanish ARU (see above).

Whenever online training and information resources were developed or made available to the project's participants, these will obviously continue to be accessible after the end of the project, increasing continuity in the educational offer for vulnerable groups.

Another element of sustainability is constituted by the personal development of the participants, in particular as regards capacity building and the setting up of relationships between operators and workers providing support to FDP. It is quite obvious that all the knowledge acquired through the TAIS and the contacts among service providers will stay after the end of the RAISD project.

Last but not least, creating strong links and cooperation agreements with the widest possible range of stakeholders, especially NGOs and CSOs, is considered one of the strongest facilitator factors for supporting the sustainability of the Project's results.

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